

SUPERSHINE

D1.4 Engagement for Social Housing refurbishment – Part 2

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
ESCO	Energy Service Companies
FVG	Friuli-Venezia Giulia Region
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LH	Lighthouse
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PV	Photovoltaic
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
QoL	Quality of Life

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SHC	Social Housing Company
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
SUPERSHINE Partner Acronym	Full name and Description
APRE	Agency for the Promotion of the European Research
ATER	Agency for Public Social Housing of Trieste
AYMING	AYMING Strategic Consultancy Company
BL	BOLIGSELSKABERNES LANDSFORENING – Danish National Association of Husing Companies
CARTIF	Fundacion CARTIF
CIRCE	Foundation Center for Research on Energy Resources and Consumption
DEMIR	DEMIR Enerji
EEIP	Energy Efficiency in Industrial Processes ASBL
EGC	European Green Cities
ENA	Agency for Environment and Energy of Arrábida
FB	FAELLESBO SHC
HE	Housing Europe - European Federation of Public, Cooperative & Social Housing
ICONS	ICONS Foundation
INSME	International Network of Small and Medium Enterprises
KM	Municipality of Kadikoy
REA	Riga Municipality Energy Agency
SPT	SPACETIME Beograd LLC
TENDER	Tendercapital Alternative Funds Plc
UoY	University of York
ZV	Zaragoza Vivienda - Public Agency for Zaragoza Housing

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the final output of Task 1.4, where the SUPERSHINE project implemented its engagement strategies for community-led co-creation, co-design and co-decision processes, developed by ICONS in D1.2. Implemented across the three SUPERSHINE Lighthouses in Riga, Herning, and Trieste, the project aligned with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principle of “Together,” focusing on inclusive district renovations, with each site at different stages of completion by the end of the project. The SUPERSHINE engagement process aims at empowering communities to co-create sustainable and aesthetically appealing neighbourhoods, while preserving cultural heritage as well. Supported by APRE, lighthouse managers exchanged innovative solutions, blending environmental, economic, and cultural considerations to meet NEB principles of sustainability and beauty. SUPERSHINE also participated actively in the NEB Community and NEB Lab to advance human-centred business models and a sustainable built environment.

Baseline and endline data comparison for Social Acceptance KPIs evaluated the impact of interventions on residents' awareness, ownership, and satisfaction, while engagement indicators measured the strategy's effectiveness. Activities included inclusive initiatives targeting diverse groups, from younger generation to marginalised communities, supported by facilitators and digital platforms to ensure widespread participation. Localised meetings and accessible materials bridged language and mobility barriers, fostering content ownership. SUPERSHINE emphasised the importance of holistic approaches in social housing refurbishment, combining technical, social, and cultural strategies: key takeaways highlight the transformative power of resident participation, unleashed by SUPERSHINE through reinforcing the role of existing social structure (e.g., the Danish “tenant democracy”) and of digital tools to overcome physical barriers (e.g., Riga's Tandeems platform), as well as by integrating cultural heritage, social cohesion, and stakeholder collaboration across the energy-efficient renovation value chain, like in the Trieste case. Lessons from the project offer a scalable framework for similar European neighbourhoods, districts, and cities (starting from the SUPERSHINE fellow cities of Belgrade, Zaragoza, Setúbal, and Istanbul), ensuring impactful and co-created community-centred solutions.

1. Introduction

The SUPERSHINE project seeks to transform social housing through active stakeholder engagement, energy-efficient renovations, and community-driven co-creation processes, aligning with the values of sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics promoted by the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

This document represents the final output of Task 1.4, focusing on the implementation, testing, and refinement of the **SUPERSHINE social acceptance model** developed by ICONS. This innovative approach aims at promoting awareness and acceptance through community-led co-creation, co-design and co-decision processes. By September 2025, the community engagement strategy across the three **SUPERSHINE Lighthouse demonstrators** have been actively implemented, in alignment with the NEB compass pillar "Together". Recognising the distinct context of each lighthouse, the engagement process followed unique timelines, with progress adapted to fit the specific roadmaps and milestones of each location. This phased approach ensures that community involvement develops organically, respecting local dynamics and promoting inclusive participation at each stage of the project.

The levels of citizen participation. Poster by Christophe Gouache – Strategic Design Scenarios, adapted from 'Ladder of Participation' (Arnstein, 1969)

The engagement vision of SUPERSHINE focused on fostering **vision co-creation (Riga), plan co-design (Trieste), and co-decision (Herning) processes**, empowering communities to lead the renovation efforts within their neighbourhoods. As part of this effort, **SUPERSHINE has contributed to creating Living Labs in the different communities**, establishing physical and digital engagement platforms where

residents can continuously collaborate, experiment, and shape the future of their districts even after the project conclusion. This legacy of trust and community spirit ensures that the process

of co-creating and evolving neighbourhoods continues beyond the project timeframe, leaving behind sustainable, engaged communities ready to take charge of future developments.

Supported by APRE, the lighthouse managers, ATER, REA, and FællesBo, maintained continuous communication, exchanging innovative technical solutions and socially impactful best practices, drawing on insights from European research and innovation. This collaborative model aimed at fulfilling the NEB principles of "Sustainable", integrating both environmental and economic dimensions, and "Beautiful", balancing aesthetic appeal with respect for culturally and historically significant architecture while ensuring practical functionality. These efforts contribute to the creation of NEB-inspired living ecosystems across Europe.

By actively engaging with the NEB Community, particularly through the NEB Lab (a space for co-creation and knowledge-sharing between NEB projects), the lighthouses exchanged practices and

expertise aimed at fostering a more sustainable and human-centred built environment. The task also included the collection of baseline data for Social Acceptance KPIs to measure the impact of SUPERSHINE interventions on residents, assessing both their awareness and acceptability, as well as their sense of ownership. These metrics evaluate how well the renovations meet residents' needs and measure changes in their attitudes, sense of belonging, and overall satisfaction. This data, in turn, informs an assessment of the social desirability and long-term well-being resulting from the renovations. Additionally, Social Engagement indicators were tracked to assess the effectiveness of the engagement strategy, identifying areas for future improvement.

The activities involved targeted engagement with diverse population groups, including young and elderly people, and marginalised communities, with the support of on-site facilitators to reach residents who may be less integrated. Localised meetings, in addition to general assemblies, ensured inclusive participation, while digital platforms enabled ongoing involvement, particularly for individuals with limited mobility. Accessibility and inclusivity were prioritised from the outset, with translated materials and questionnaires helping to overcome language barriers, ensuring that all participants could take ownership of the content.

1.1. Structure of the document

This deliverable presents the implementation process related to the engagement strategies and methodologies developed under the SUPERSHINE project in T1.2 and T1.3 to address the socio-economic and technical challenges associated with the sustainable refurbishment of social housing. The document focuses on three pilot sites, the SUPERSHINE lighthouses of Riga (Latvia), Herning (Denmark), and Trieste (Italy).

The document is the continuation of **D1.3 – Engagement for Social Housing Refurbishment – Part 1**, submitted in December 2024, that presented the strategic setting and the first phase of the engagement implementation. After the introduction, D1.4 moves to **Section 2 – Social Engagement Activities**: the first subsection, **2.1 – Engagement Activities and Monitoring**, is divided in three macro-paragraphs, one per each Lighthouse. Therefore, for each one, the document provides a **context overview and engagement roadmap summary**, to recap the demographic, economic, and infrastructural profiles of each site, framing the challenges faced by their respective communities, as well as the respective steps of the tailored **participatory roadmap** (defined by ICONS in D1.2). Then, the **methodological framework** for the co-creation, co-design, and co-decision implementation is briefly presented, followed by a graphic representation of the **engagement implementation timeline**, in order to better clarify the context before the reporting of the **actual implementation of the participatory activities**. This part is followed by an **analysis of the Social Engagement KPIs** with regards to the respective activities.

Subsection 2.2, Social Acceptance Analysis and Monitoring, focuses on measuring residents' perceptions of renovating interventions using the tailored questionnaires developed by ICONS, created to monitor the SUPERSHINE Social Acceptance KPIs. This section links the technical and social dimensions of the project, ensuring that renovations align with community needs and gain widespread acceptance. At first, for each lighthouse, the baseline datum is analysed, followed by the endline datum, providing insights on the acceptance variation consequent to the active participation of the communities in envisioning the renovation of their districts.

This document also contains **replicability inputs (Section 3)**, distilling lessons learnt from the lighthouses into a framework for adapting these strategies to other European contexts, especially those of the four SUPERSHINE fellow cities, Belgrade (Serbia), Zaragoza (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), and Istanbul (Turkey). This section identifies best practices for scalability and replication

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of the SUPERSHINE integrated approach embedded into the engagement pathway and social acceptance assessment, such as integrating innovative financing models, community-led initiatives, and participatory governance mechanisms.

Finally, the **key takeaways aspects** and the **conclusions (Section 4 and 5)** synthesise the outcomes of the qualitative and quantitative analysis on the three engagement pathways, emphasising the project dual goals of improving energy efficiency and enhancing social cohesion through resident engagement.

The **Annex (Section 6)** report the social acceptance questionnaire, developed by ICONS, as a reference.

2. Social Engagement Activities

2.1. Engagement Activities and Monitoring

2.1.1. Riga – Latvia

Context overview and engagement roadmap summary

The Riga Lighthouse, situated in the Āgenskalna Priedes residential district, represents both a significant historical milestone and a testing ground for innovative approaches to sustainable urban renewal. Constructed between 1959 and 1961 as Latvia's first large-scale residential complex, the district today encompasses twenty-five buildings and accommodates more than 2,700 residents.

The community is ethnically diverse, with Latvians, Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, Poles, Jews, and Lithuanians represented, while the average age slightly exceeds the city's mean. Despite modest income levels, relatively low unemployment and municipal support mechanisms provide some stability. However, the housing stock suffers from poor energy performance, inadequate comfort, and long-standing disrepair. Cultural and linguistic barriers, combined with historically low civic participation, have complicated collective decision-making, thereby making participatory approaches to refurbishment both challenging and essential

To address these challenges, the Riga Lighthouse has adopted a structured engagement roadmap designed to anchor the district's transformation in **citizen co-creation and co-design of the vision for the future integrated district renewal**. The approach, elaborated by the Riga Energy Agency (REA) in collaboration with ICONS, treats residents not as passive beneficiaries but as protagonists of the process, actively contributing to the design, planning, and prioritisation of interventions. Engagement has been facilitated through workshops, advisory groups, and the digital platform *Tandeems*, ensuring that the evolving vision for the neighbourhood is rooted in the perspectives and aspirations of its inhabitants.

The first phase, **Awareness and launch of activities**, started in June 2023 with a large neighbourhood festival, establishing first contact with residents, introducing the aims of the SUPERSHINE project, and collecting baseline data for social acceptance. Furthermore, it created the conditions for dialogue, trust-building, and the recognition of residents' concerns as the foundation for subsequent co-design activities. The second phase, **Planning of interventions**, centred on **co-designing the renewal vision** for the district. Meetings with the city architect, thematic seminars, and the formation of a resident advisory group enabled deliberation on renovation strategies, aesthetic preferences, and financial models. A series of co-design workshops brought together around 80 participants to collaboratively define façade treatments, the reorganisation of cellars and courtyards, and the management of shared green areas. The *Tandeems* platform extended participation by allowing residents to submit proposals, vote on alternatives, and visualise architectural options, thus combining digital inclusiveness with face-to-face deliberation. The third phase, **Implementation of works**, started in 2025 with REA and the City of Riga's efforts to transform the envisioned renovation plan into practice, working towards official approval, as well as for diverse source of funding. A **homeowners' association was formalised**, with technical and procedural guidance from the REA, thus creating the necessary legal and financial entity to oversee renovation planning and execution. Parallel efforts have been dedicated to monitor social perception, through a final administration of the SUPERSHINE

questionnaire, after the conclusion of the engagement pathway, measuring how co-creation processes have influenced attitudes and sense of ownership. Documentation through interviews, photography, and video will disseminate the results and highlight the transformative impact of citizen-led design choices in the final months of the year. The fourth phase, **Consolidation and monitoring**, will carry on the SUPERSHINE legacy from 2026 onwards: strengthening long-term ownership by embedding co-created solutions into community practices. Resident-led management structures for green and communal areas are expected to consolidate empowerment, while a feasibility study will assess how this **co-created model of district renovation** can be replicated in other urban contexts

The Riga Lighthouse has thus embraced a participatory methodology where the **vision for transformation emerges directly from the community itself**. By combining digital innovation with traditional assemblies, the process has overcome linguistic, cultural, and generational barriers, while participatory budgeting has provided tangible means for residents to shape their environment. In conclusion, the Riga engagement roadmap illustrates how **integrated renewal co-creation can transform socio-economic complexity into collective strength**. By progressing through successive phases of awareness, planning, implementation, and consolidation, the district refurbishment is not only enhancing energy efficiency and living conditions but also cultivating a renewed sense of belonging and agency among residents, in alignment with the New European Bauhaus principles of sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetic quality.

Co-creation for district renovation in Āgenskalna priedes: an overview of the framework

The Riga Lighthouse adopted a holistic approach that not only addresses the buildings but also focuses on the sustainability of the neighbourhood living ecosystem. It emphasised collective efforts in mitigating and adapting to climate change, promoting sustainable mobility, green infrastructure, and nature-based solutions. Additionally, it integrated renewable energy sources (RES) and harnesses the benefits of digital technologies, all contributing to the overall enhancement of the quality of life, well-being, and health of the district's residents.

The Āgenskalna priedes community implemented a process of co-designing the district overall renewal, layered on three different levels of intervention:

- The building level.
- The common areas and innyards level.
- The entire district intended as a whole.

The co-design has been carried out through a specific double-faceted approach, using both digital support tools for citizen engagement as well as other types of discussion spaces to keep the district community always in touch, i.e. the digital platform “Tandeems¹”. Tandeems is an original Latvian platform, developed by REA and the NGO Tandeems, created for conducting online design competitions and workshops, and that includes a library of tools to fit a variety of competition formats, educational tasks and user surveys. The goal was to cultivate a transparent, digital and competitive co-design process that can meaningfully engage local community, various user groups, general public and experts, through activities going from architectural intervention modelling, to focus groups and online workshops, and physical workshops with the district community. This layered approach

¹ <https://tandeems.lv/contests/agenskalna-priedes>

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allowed the Riga lighthouse to widen its audience beyond the selected community, exchanging ideas and validating the most technical proposals of professionals in the sector.

During the physical workshops with the community stakeholders, the participants co-designed the development vision and strategy for the energy retrofits and revitalisation of the whole housing block. Up to September 2025, the lighthouse of Riga carried out a community-led co-designing of the block, making customised architectural visualisations of future renovation and growth of the district, also developing plans to use the participatory budget from the City of Riga to renovate inn-yards and communal green areas, in order to directly assign the management on to the community, therefore creating new jobs for self-maintenance.

It is also worth noting that all activities incorporated an element of bottom-up participation. At the conclusion of each event, residents of the Riga demonstration site proposed various topics and voted on those they would prefer to see addressed in future engagement activities.

Furthermore, in Riga, the stakeholders showed a significant interest to be further involved in the SUPERSHINE process leading to the customisation of their lighthouse business models, and were regularly updated by REA about their SUPERSHINE meetings with the consortium partners involved in the activity (UoY, CIRCE, AYMING, TENDER). This interest was due to the difficulties previously encountered by the Riga Municipality in negotiating with the government traditional forms of top-down funding schemes (so far never tested in Latvia), leading REA to start from the SUPERSHINE results for the possibility of co-designing, together with the community, a business model for bottom-up funding schemes, allowing each building in the district to have its own financial scheme.

Engagement timeline

Kick-off of the engagement activities

The kick-off event of the SUPERSHINE engagement path was held in June 2023 during the Quarter Festivity, that represented an important opportunity to introduce the SUPERSHINE project to local residents and establish the first networks of collaboration, despite the engagement strategy was yet in the process of being defined in its objectives and peculiarities.

With a participatory approach, active citizens were engaged, forming a direct link for future events. Although the event was somewhat costly, it proved to be a valuable investment for long-term collaboration with the local community. While most participants (more than one hundred in total) showed little interest in the technical aspects of the project, it became clear that presenting clear

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goals and a defined timeline is essential to maintain engagement and encourage ongoing involvement.

A shot from the kick-off in Riga

‘Community-led development’ workshop

The aim of this workshop was to establish a connection between the chief architect of Riga and the residents, providing an opportunity to discuss his vision for the potential development of the quarter, as well as gather input from the inhabitants on possible solutions. However, the constructive engagement with residents was hindered by the architect's presentation of the proposed solution, which was not well thought out. Despite this, valuable input was collected from the community regarding their concerns and ideas.

The workshop proved that, despite the enthusiasm and the positive attitude from the community side, clear communication is crucial at all times from the practitioners, that should be able to communicate the innovation of intended solutions in an accessible manner, especially when residents might perceive certain proposals as a threat to the peace of their daily lives.

Similar to the kick-off event, this workshop was held for logistics and experts' availabilities reasons before the SUPERSHINE engagement strategy by ICONS was completed. Therefore, REA, as pilot manager, made good use of this experience by working with ICONS in having the SUPERSHINE engagement strategy tailored to tackle this communication barrier among the technical experts and the district inhabitants.

Scenes from the 'community-led development' workshop

The SUPERSHINE Hackathon

For the seventh consecutive year, in November 2023, Riga hosted the influential international urban planning forum "MadCity 2023", thus fostering collaboration and innovation in the city's urban development. The "MadCity 2023" forum brought together urban planners, architects, municipal experts, and other interested parties with a shared goal: to co-create innovative solutions that would help transform the Āgenskalna priedes district and other micro-districts of Riga into vibrant, thriving communities.

Among the key events during the forum, the Mayor of Riga, Vilnis Kīrisis, visited the Āgenskalna priedes district to meet with residents. He engaged in meaningful conversations, answering their questions about the potential future development of the area from a municipal perspective. In addition, a hackathon was organised, where participants focused on brainstorming creative ideas for the quarter's development.

The event was dedicated to addressing one of Riga's most pressing urban challenges: the revitalisation and re-humanisation of Soviet-era micro-districts, raising the issue of dissonant architectural heritage. In addition to recalling a recent and problematic past, the Sovietic areas face numerous issues, including ageing housing, outdated public spaces, and a lack of urban environments that promote social interaction and cooperation among residents. During the forum, new and unconventional solutions were developed, with the aim of making the Āgenskalna priedes district a more enjoyable, integrated, and sustainable place to live.

Images from the SUPERSHINE hackathon at 'MadCity 23' festival.

'Energy retrofits' workshop

The "Energy retrofits" workshop brought together the lead energy efficiency expert from REA, with a particular focus on building renovation. It was part of REA's regular One-stop-shop service, which provides consultations on building renovations. What set this session apart from business as usual was its SUPERSHINE-inspired focus on the single district of Āgenskalna priedes, which raised unique questions and considerations, resulting from direct and active involvement of the district tenants, such as exploring potential cost-saving opportunities under the framework of SUPERSHINE innovative financial tools analysis.

As with all One-stop-shop meetings, the consultants involved were expected to be well-versed in a range of topics, offering expertise across various aspects of building renovation. However, when questions arose that could not be immediately answered, it was essential that a clear pathway be provided to the consultee, ensuring they knew how to access the required information at a later stage. To meet this need, the SUPERSHINE toolkit will be further integrated and put at community's disposal, and this aspect was taken into consideration by the SUPERSHINE consortium in the process of shaping the project's own one-stop-shop, currently in elaboration phase.

Shots from the 'Energy retrofits' workshop

'Reinforcing the community values' workshop

Shot from the event

The purpose of the meeting was to help residents shape a vision for their urban living ecosystem, thus to be rooted in shared values. While the focus was on fostering this new way of thinking, the topic of building renovation also emerged briefly.

By the end of the meeting, a solid foundation had been laid for creating a value-driven vision for the area. The residents were introduced to a fresh perspective on how to approach the development of their community, one that might have felt different from their usual way of thinking.

However, in hindsight, the meeting may have been too broad in scope. The inclusion of building

renovation discussions, while relevant, ended up distracting from the main goal. A more focused approach, that is to say centred solely on the vision for the district, might have yielded even more meaningful insights and clearer direction.

'Visioning the future' workshop

Vērtības balstīta
Āgenskalna priekšu kvartāla
attīstības vīzija – semināru cikls

2. seminārs –
Kāds izskatās mūsu nākotnes
kvartāls?

3. jūnijā plkst. 18.30
Pie skulpturka-strādnieka Āgenskalna ielā 24

Darīsim kvartāla kopā ar arhitektu
un plānotājiem, izvērtējam
labiekārtošanas iespējas!

Lūdzam zvanīt šim
numuram: 30. maijā
ej uz /seminars2AP

Finansējums:
Āgenskalna priekšu
kvartāla attīstībai
no Āgenskalna ielā 24

Event poster

During this workshop, the team of architects from the NGO Tandeems was introduced to the district inhabitants, and a potential collaboration with them was outlined (that would have then resulted in the shared Tandeems platform for the Riga lighthouse co-design process).

To engage the residents, the event included a walking tour where participants took photos of the areas they least liked in the quarter, capturing them at different planning scales. The residents then proposed possible improvements for these spots, which were later shared and voted on through the Tandeems digital platform, back then in the early development phase.

This marked the launch of a digital participation process, giving the inhabitants a chance to contribute their ideas and feedback on potential

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During the sessions, clear tasks and schedules were established for the next steps: some participants were tasked with contributing to building renovation efforts, while others took part in a communal gardening project in the quarter, bringing a sense of collaboration to the process.

It became evident that connecting the residents through the shared history of the district was an effective approach, also to support them in dealing with the Soviet legacy and the dissonant architectural heritage. This narrative not only sparked interest but also helped to build a sense of community, with a clearer sense of ownership towards their homes compared to the past. Moving forward, it emerged that, for future activities to succeed, responsibility and communication channels must be clearly defined, ensuring everyone knows their role and how to stay informed.

'Vision and next steps' poster agenda and shots

As a result of the SUPERSHINE co-design participatory path, the Āgenskalna priedes district inhabitants produced concrete materials containing their community-shaped vision for the future radical renovation of the district. Some of those materials are presented in the pictures below.

Renders and maps of the community-shaped vision for the district

Big clean-up community event

The day was dedicated to a hands-on co-working session focused on the tangible aspect of building renovation. A flower-bed feature in the quarter was cleared of debris, and the ground was levelled where needed, transforming the space with visible effort and teamwork.

The community participating the clean-up event

This event turned out to be more than just a practical task: it became a strong communal experience, one that brought people together through shared work and common interests. By the end of the day, there was a clear, rewarding result that everyone could take pride in.

Such short-term activities play a crucial role in uniting a community, especially when larger projects like building renovation can span years. Without these smaller, more immediate actions, it is easy for the connection between neighbours to fade, leaving the community feeling disconnected from one another in the long wait for bigger changes.

Residents' assembly to formalise a homeowners association

At the beginning of 2025, a residents' assembly was convened for the four interconnected condominium properties located at Kristapa Street 16, 16a, 16b and 16c, with the primary objective of formalising their homeowners association. Approximately sixty unit owners participated in the initial session, during which, with technical and procedural guidance from the REA, the association was duly established, thereby creating the necessary legal and financial entity to oversee renovation planning and execution. During the first part of 2025, subsequent meetings were held, though with diminishing attendance, and to date no loan agreement has been concluded. The principal impediment remains the suspension of the State support programme for residential renovation, which is critical for financial viability. In the case of conjoined housing units, a coordinated quarter-based approach is essential to ensure cost-efficiency and structural coherence, making the current lack of state-backed incentives a significant barrier to project advancement.

A shot from the residents' assembly

Site visit to recently renovated building to discuss organisational aspects of renovation

A site visit was organised to a recently renovated residential building within the quarter, undertaken jointly with the REVERTER project on a 50-50 implementation basis. During the visit, structured

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discussions were held with both the residents of the renovated property and the project manager, providing first-hand insights into the technical, financial, and organisational aspects of the renovation process. The activity successfully engaged approximately thirty participants directly, generating significant interest among homeowners. Demonstration visits of this nature have proven to be an effective outreach tool, as exposure to a completed renovation increases motivation among residents of non-renovated dwellings. This methodological approach is intended to be further integrated into the programme of activities coordinated by Riga's One-Stop-Shop, serving as a replicable model for community engagement and knowledge transfer.

The residents' joining the site visit

2.1.1.1. Monitoring of SE KPIs

Table 1 below presents the Social Engagement KPIs collected by the Riga demo site for the activities described in 4.1.1. This set of KPIs evaluates the effectiveness of engagement in demo sites, addressing factors such as the ratio between target participants and actual attendees. The KPIs are the means to monitor the implementation of the engagement roadmap described in detail in D1.2, covering *Phase 1: Awareness/Launch of activities*, and *Phase 2: Design of renovations works*.

The demo case constitutes a pivotal example as all activities included some form of capacity building content. During each event, Riga city experts from the Energy Renovation OSS and other municipal departments engaged directly with residents, delivering presentations and responding to questions on topics such as energy retrofits, energy efficiency of building stock, revitalisation of adjacent public space, legal procedures, available funding and financial aid programmes to support energy renovation projects. Municipalities and external experts showcased best practices and lessons learned from past energy retrofits, different technologies of renovation of the building and its engineering systems, details on costs and benefits, and explaining legal aspects for the preparation of energy retrofit projects. Furthermore, all presentations and workshop materials were consistently shared with event participants and uploaded to the Tandeems digital participation platform. This approach enables all activities described in 4.1.1 to be recognized as capacity building activities, contributing directly to the measurement of KPI4.SE.

Measurements of KPI11.SE indicate that engagement targets were reached in most of activities. Notably, the first three activities, primarily focused on engaging on the community of residents, gathered more participants than expected, signalling a good responsiveness of the residents to

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engagement activities. However, three activities fell short of their participation target: the ‘Energy retrofits’ workshop, the ‘Big clean-up’ community event, and the inhabitant meeting. These activities differed significantly in nature and audience, targeting design experts and residents. As such, no single factor can be attributed to the lower engagement in both cases. When cross-referenced with Social Awareness indicators KPI1.SA and KPI2.SA, as reported in 4.2.2.1 (baseline data), the lower participation for the ‘Energy retrofits’ workshop may reflect a limited level of awareness and interest among residents regarding energy production and management. Similarly, lower participation to the inhabitant meeting can be attributed to the persistent low awareness among residents even after the project’s implementations.

Table 1: Social Engagement Indicators for Riga demo site

KPI code and name	Stakeholder Outreach (KPI1.SE)	Stakeholders Groups (KPI2.SE)	Capacity building activities (KPI4.SE)
KPI definition	This KPI measures the number of stakeholders engaged in the LH for each activity conducted (e.g., co-design sessions, capacity building sessions, community events) according to the target set.	This KPI assesses the participation of all stakeholders’ groups that the activity aims to engage in the event. For instance, if a workshop involving tenants, students and local association has been planned, it is important to verify that all stakeholders’ groups have participated.	Number of SHs reached by capacity building activities or material prepared
Unit of measurement	%	%	Number
Engagement Activity 1: Kick-off of the engagement activities – 06.06.2023	(120 participants / 100 target) = 120%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	120
Engagement Activity 2: ‘Community-led development’ workshop – 30.10.2023	(37 participants / 30 target) = 123%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	37
Engagement Activity 3: The SUPERSHINE Hackathon – 02.10.2023	(400 participants / 300 target) = 133%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	400
Engagement Activity 4: ‘Energy retrofits’ workshop – 15.01.2024	(44 participants / 50 target) = 88%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	44
Engagement Activity 5: ‘Reinforcing the community values’ workshop – 29.04.2024	(31 participants / 30 target) = 103%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	31

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Engagement Activity 6: 'Visioning the future' workshop – 03.06.2024	(34 participants / 30 target) = 113%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	34
Engagement Activity 7: 'Development of the potential renewal (buildings and innyards)' workshop – 22.07.2024	(50 participants / 50 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	50
Engagement Activity 8: Regular workshops for 'Vision and Next Steps' – 19.08.2024	(70 participants / 50 target) = 140%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	70
Engagement Activity 9: Big clean-up community event – 28.09.2024	(8 participants / 15 target) = 53%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	8
Engagement Activity 10: inhabitant meeting – 14.01.2025	(37 participants / 40 target) = 92,5%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	40
Engagement Activity 11: Trip to renovated house – 11.03.2025.	(30 participants / 15 target) = 200%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	15

2.1.2. Herning – Denmark

Context overview and engagement roadmap summary

As better described in D1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, In Herning, situated in the Danish Midtjylland Region, the SUPERSHINE project focuses on the FaellesBo district, a residential area that reflects both the strengths and the challenges of contemporary social housing. The district combines the advantages of low-density living with solid access to public services, such as schools, healthcare facilities, shopping centres, cultural hubs, and well-developed cycling and public transport networks. Yet, beneath this favourable infrastructure, residents face persistent socio-economic difficulties. While around 70% of the population is employed, educational attainment remains uneven, with half of residents lacking formal qualifications. Household incomes vary widely, creating a pronounced economic stratification within the community. Social patterns add further complexity: nearly seven out of ten households consist of individuals living alone, a significant proportion of whom are single parents, and one fifth of residents have a migrant background. These demographic realities introduce cultural and generational divides which, in turn, influence participation in community initiatives and perceptions of renovation programmes.

The FaellesBo housing stock itself, built largely between 1954 and 1965 and partially renovated in the 1980s and 1990s, was showing clear signs of obsolescence and is therefore undergoing an integrated process of renovation and retrofitting, in order to meet current energy efficiency standards. Furthermore, structural and technological modernisation was urgently needed, not only

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to reduce environmental impact but also to improve comfort, functionality, and the well-being of tenants. Against this backdrop, SUPERSHINE supports a broad renovation vision, targeting the integration of renewable energy sources (especially PV systems), advanced energy management systems, urban reforestation projects, and community-based labs for recycling of materials from demolished district buildings. This renovation ambition is paired with a social one: ensuring that tenants remain active co-creators of their future living environment.

Tenant democracy (source: KAB Memo)

Central to this participatory effort is Denmark unique model of **tenant democracy**, a cornerstone of the national non-profit housing system. Rooted in cooperative traditions and strengthened through the welfare state, tenant democracy grants residents the right to influence every stage of housing management, from daily affairs to major investment decisions. In practice, tenants elect representatives to estate-level boards, which collaborate with professional managers on operational matters, and these representatives also feed into broader assemblies that guide organisational strategies. Renovation projects cannot proceed without tenant approval, typically secured through

general assemblies, where residents debate and vote on proposals. The system ensures that housing decisions reflect collective priorities, while rents are reinvested into upkeep, improvements, and social initiatives. Funds are also pooled across the sector, through national entities such as the National Building Foundation, to guarantee equity between estates. This governance model strengthens accountability, fosters community ownership, and provides a fertile ground for participatory innovation, such as that promoted by SUPERSHINE.

Building on this democratic foundation, the engagement roadmap for Herning was structured into four interlinked phases. The first, the **Awareness Phase**, sought to inform residents about the project goals and anticipated benefits, while collecting baseline data through social acceptance questionnaires. These activities gauged perceptions of proposed changes and provided a benchmark for measuring impact over time. The second, the **Planning Phase**, introduced co-decision and co-design processes that gave residents a direct role in shaping interventions. Each of the four planned lines of action (installation of photovoltaic systems with battery storage, optimisation of heat management, biodiversity promotion through urban reforestation and green space revitalisation, and reuse of construction materials via community-based labs) was discussed with tenants to refine technical and financial arrangements. The third, the **Implementation Phase**, focused on carrying out the planned works while embedding capacity-building opportunities. Training sessions enabled tenants to familiarise themselves with new technologies, such as energy management tools, and to engage in practical initiatives, from biodiversity-friendly gardening to recycling practices. Finally, the **Consolidation Phase**, due for the upcoming years, will emphasise the long-term sustainability of the Community Hub of FællesBo tenants, and the outcomes of their co-decision and co-design pathway, through ongoing education, behavioural change programmes, and endline measurements of social acceptance to be compared with the initial baseline. This phase also considers the replicability of the Herning model, assessing how its blend of tenant democracy, technical innovation, and social equity can inform similar efforts across Europe.

The Herning lighthouse thus demonstrates how a housing renovation project can transcend purely technical objectives. By combining the Danish tenant democracy tradition with structured phases

of awareness, planning, implementation, and consolidation, SUPERSHINE is enabling residents not merely to accept, but to lead, the transition towards energy efficiency and sustainability. In doing so, Herning exemplifies how participatory governance can underpin a fair green transition, balancing environmental imperatives with social cohesion and inclusivity.

Co-decision for district renovation in FællesBo: an overview of the framework

The implementation of the SUPERSHINE project in FællesBo district aimed at reducing energy poverty issues by decreasing the high cost of energy bills (especially heating costs) through the installation of Photovoltaic Systems, establishing Electric Vehicles charging stations makes it possible for the tenants to apply EV (both scooters, bikes, and cars), and rewilding green areas to increase life quality in the near surroundings. Furthermore, in addition to co-decision with the district tenants, several stakeholders, such as associations for social promotions, universities, artists, start-up SMEs, local designers & architects, NGOs, local investors were encouraged to contribute and co-design district activities, also widening the social engagement audience to the neighbouring community.

As aforementioned, under the aegis of SUPERSHINE, the Faellesbo district is developing co-decision and co-design paths with the community relating to four areas of intervention planned for the area:

- Energy management technologies.
- Urban reforestation.
- Community-based labs for recycling of district building materials.
- Photovoltaic systems instalment.

Concerning **Smart Energy Management**, the lighthouse manager investigated, together with the community, whether they can use Danfoss ECL, intelligent temperature controllers for district heating (DH), district cooling (DC), domestic hot water systems (DHW), and ventilation systems, in all the district housing departments. The community was directly involved in the decision-making, collaborating with project experts to assess energy savings by reviewing consumption data, energy labels, and other relevant metrics.

In the departments under renovation (Departments 16, 19, 21, and 24), Danfoss ECL has also been used, with Neogrid Preheat implemented in demonstration blocks in Department 24. However, these departments are still under renovation.

Up to September 2025, the community is in the process of identifying other departments with the greatest potential for energy savings. A challenge is that while energy savings directly benefit the residents through a reduction in their energy bills, the employment of an energy specialist would need to be financed through the rent (operating budget). This presents a dilemma, and for residents to understand this, it is crucial to communicate the situation effectively. The community aims at working systematically with energy data collection and analysis to demonstrate the benefits of allowing a rent increase, with the expectation that residents' consumption will decrease correspondingly, or even more, as a result.

If energy savings are realised, the community will explore whether these savings could be reinvested to finance the employment of an energy specialist, who would continuously ensure energy savings and assist in engaging residents in using new technologies and managing energy more effectively.

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With regards to **PV systems**, a pilot solar panel system was installed in Department 16 in 2023, and the renovation of the department was completed in January 2025. The energy savings generated by the solar system have been evenly distributed among all residents in the department, resulting in a reduction in their kWh prices. However, it will not be until the end of 2025 that a full year-worth of data will be available to assess the long-term effects.

The community initially considered installing solar panel systems in Departments 19, 21, and 24. However, these systems would need to be financed through the rent unless financed through an ESCO. After evaluating the long-term costs and commitments of ESCO financing, the community decided that this solution was too expensive and opted not to proceed with it for these departments.

Instead, the solar panel system in Department 16 was financed through the master plan, with the costs covered via the rent, as required by law. The initial idea was to implement ESCO financing, where the system would be financed by Sydbank and the loan repayments covered by the energy savings. However, this model was not legally permissible under BL (Danish housing legislation) unless an ESCO supplier was involved. As a result, the community chose the master plan route to comply with the legal requirements.

If the results in Department 16 prove successful, it will be easier, with supporting data, to argue for the installation of solar panels in other departments through a rent increase, where energy savings are expected to exceed the rent adjustment.

Concerning the **community-led laboratory for the reuse of demolished building materials**, an orangery in Department 16, built using recycled materials, was completed in 2023. The project, which involved active participation from the local vocational school, has proven to be a successful collaboration. The orangery is now in use by residents, the social master plan, the nearby school, daycare institutions, the youth school UngHerning, and the local activity centre. During a recent visit, the orangery was being used by a large family of non-Danish ethnic background for a children's birthday party. The department board has decided that the orangery should be open to anyone who treats it well.

The tool shed and fire hut, also constructed using recycled materials, have been completed. These were built in collaboration with the company Næste and a local carpentry company, Bent Jensen, with carpentry apprentices from the vocational school involved in the project. These apprentices were students without an apprenticeship placement and were therefore in school-based training. The project was an exciting and educational opportunity for the students.

The environmental sustainability focus of these initiatives includes the use of recycled materials, CO₂ reduction, and the multifunctional use of facilities, which can serve multiple target groups and reduce the need for new construction elsewhere.

The social sustainability aspect aims to foster social communities, increase well-being, reduce loneliness, and provide apprenticeships, potentially improving young people's attachment to the labour market in Herning.

For the **rewilding and urban nature projects**, the community has now established its "green and blue oasis" with meadow flowers, beehives, a fruit grove, a wetland area with integrated play, and raised beds, all adjacent to the tool shed. This initiative is intended to inspire other departments, particularly by exploring whether savings can be achieved in operations when implementing wilder solutions that require less maintenance.

In collaboration with Fruehøjgaard Boligselskab and supported by the SUPERSHINE team, the community is developing an inspiration catalogue that will serve as a resource for all Danish housing

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departments. The project is also looking into whether operational savings could help finance further rewilding initiatives, fostering long-term environmental sustainability within the community.

This initiative is also working closely with the “Sustainable Herning” association, other local social housing companies, and their respective boards of tenants. Additionally, a pilot project is underway to introduce meadow flowers and wetlands as part of climate adaptation measures in FaellesBo’s green common areas.

Engagement timeline

Questionnaire-focused meeting

Considering their role as spokesmen for the tenants of the lighthouse, the Board of Tenants was appointed with the role of collecting information concerning the sentiment of the community in terms of social acceptance of the renovations. Therefore, they organised a meeting to answer the SUPERSHINE social acceptance questionnaire with pre-aggregated data representing groups of tenants, thus providing the baseline datum for the social acceptance analysis. The responses provided by the Board of Tenants painted an overwhelmingly positive picture. The feedback highlighted high levels of social acceptance and enthusiasm for the pilot project, which focuses on energy management, photovoltaic systems, the reuse of building materials, and rewilding initiatives.

This encouraging outcome will serve as a cornerstone for the further development and implementation of the SUPERSHINE pilot activities, ensuring that these innovative solutions resonate deeply with the community's aspirations and support their long-term sustainability. The SUPERSHINE project stood out as a transformative initiative, and the tenants showed enthusiasm towards the perspective of receiving an appealing and community-centred financing models tailored to support the renovation actions in the Faellesbo district. As soon as these financing solutions are refined and presented, the questionnaire will be administered again to collect the endline datum, which will presumably be improved in terms of trusting the project’s dedication to not just innovation, but also to genuine collaboration and tenant empowerment, having offered meaningful and realistic outcomes.

PV systems pilot installation validation and co-decision meeting

FÆLLESBO’s initiative to install PV systems reflects its commitment to driving positive economic returns from its investments. With this goal in mind, FÆLLESBO organised informational meetings

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with the tenants of Department 16 to discuss the possibility of installing PV panels. The response was overwhelmingly positive, reflecting the tenants' enthusiasm for sustainable energy solutions. As a cooperative housing association, Danish social housing companies like FÆLLESBO rely on tenant approval to move forward with such projects. Encouraged by the supportive feedback, the tenants' board of Department 16 approved the PV investment, leading to the successful installation of the system in late 2023.

However, following this milestone, FÆLLESBO's administration received new guidance from BL, the Danish Association of Housing Cooperatives (SHCs), which posed an unexpected challenge. For Danish SHCs, the economic benefits of PV investments could not be directly realised by tenants. Instead, the gross cost of the investment would need to be absorbed as a rental expense, diminishing the appeal of PV installations for tenants. Recognising this barrier, FÆLLESBO began exploring innovative financing models to make future PV investments viable and attractive, with the support of SUPERSHINE financial partners. Solutions under consideration include ESCO financing and crowd-financing models, which could address the economic challenges and create pathways for more equitable and tenant-friendly investments.

The SUPERSHINE project plays a pivotal role in this effort. By leveraging its resources and collaborative framework, FÆLLESBO aims at identifying and testing these new financing models, setting the stage for sustainable energy solutions that benefit both the environment and the tenants. SUPERSHINE thus becomes a key enabler in turning these ambitious goals into actionable outcomes.

Stakeholders' dialogue for financing PV systems

As previously noted, the lighthouse manager needed to account for the fact that, under a business-as-usual approach, the full investment cost of PV installation would need to be incorporated into tenants' rent. This requirement has understandably led to tenants' reluctance to support the adoption of PV systems. In response to this challenge, FÆLLESBO is exploring innovative financing mechanisms, such as ESCO financing, to mitigate this obstacle and enhance the investment's appeal.

To initiate this process, Fællesbo has engaged with six key stakeholders to identify viable financing models for PV systems. These stakeholders include the ESCO SUSTAIN Solutions, an energy expert, the FÆLLESBO Handcraft Department, the FÆLLESBO Organisation Board, BL, other local SHCs, and the local electricity DSO company.

The pilot installation of PV panels in the district

There has been strong interest among the stakeholders to collaborate with FÆLLESBO in finding effective financing solutions for PV investments. One promising avenue is ESCO financing, and SUSTAIN Solutions is currently working on a proposal for this model. For instance, an example from the SUSTAIN Technologies website, that can be seen in the picture, highlights a successful PV project for the SHC Sønderborg Andelsboligforening, offering insights into the potential for similar solutions.

Stakeholder-led administrative sessions for the construction of an orangery

The orangery worksite.

FÆLLESBO embarked on an innovative project to create an orangery in a shared green space, using salvaged materials from building renovations. To bring this sustainable vision to life, securing a building permit from Herning Municipality was a necessary first step. Recognising the importance of collaboration, four key stakeholders from the district community joined forces to prepare the application: Herning Municipality; Næste, a construction company specialising in material reuse and tasked with building the orangery; Titan, a demolition company involved in FÆLLESBO's renovation projects and the provider of the reused materials; and FÆLLESBO itself, coordinating the effort.

This cooperative approach proved to be a resounding success. By aligning the expertise and contributions of these stakeholders, FÆLLESBO not only streamlined the permit process but also laid a strong foundation for the orangery project. This positive experience has inspired FÆLLESBO to explore broader applications of material reuse, envisioning new constructions that incorporate salvaged materials on a larger scale.

However, FÆLLESBO is mindful of potential challenges. Securing building permits for reuse projects, managing additional costs tied to demolition processes, and addressing expenses related to adapting reused materials for new constructions are all hurdles that require careful consideration. To navigate these challenges, FÆLLESBO plans to analyse the results of the orangery project, using it as a blueprint to inform future strategies and initiatives.

With this groundwork, FÆLLESBO is poised to expand its material reuse efforts, demonstrating how innovative partnerships and sustainable practices can reshape the construction landscape while fostering environmental responsibility.

Regular meetings to involve students from the Herningsholm Business Academy

As part of its efforts to promote the reuse of building materials, FÆLLESBO embarked on an inspiring initiative: constructing an orangery in a shared green space using materials salvaged from renovation projects. To bring this vision to life, FÆLLESBO reached out to the local Herningsholm Business Academy, an institution dedicated to training young people in craftsmanship and technical professions. Enthusiastically embracing the collaboration, Herningsholm involved fifteen of its students in the project, working alongside twenty tenants from the community, and established a series of meeting to present the vision and the approaches for this collaboration.

The Academy students brought valuable technical expertise to the table, contributing significantly to the planning and execution of the orangery. Their knowledge of building materials and techniques proved instrumental in guiding tenants through the process, ensuring the project was both innovative and practical. While the physical construction of the orangery was completed by a professional

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A shot from one of the meetings

building company, the collaboration highlighted the power of combining educational resources with community-driven initiatives.

The success of this partnership is encouraging FÆLLESBO to explore further collaborations with Herningsholm

Building the orangery

Business Academy. Plans are underway to extend this approach to other reuse projects and potentially even broader initiatives, such as rewilding efforts, photovoltaic systems, and more. FÆLLESBO is also considering partnerships with additional educational institutions, leveraging specialised expertise to amplify the impact of its sustainability projects.

This fruitful alliance demonstrates how merging education, community engagement, and sustainability can yield extraordinary results, setting a precedent for future ventures.

Community-led building of a garden shed and a fireplace

As part of its commitment to sustainability, FÆLLESBO launched an inspiring project to build a garden shed and fireplace in a shared green space, using reclaimed materials from renovation activities as per the orangery. FÆLLESBO partnered again with Herningsholm Business Academy, involving the students.

The involvement of Academy pupils, with their know-how about technical issues related to buildings and construction materials, has shown up to be successful in supporting FÆLLESBO tenants in planning and implementing the garden shed and fire place re-using building materials from building renovation. Yet, as per the orangery, for security reasons, the final building of the garden shed and the fireplace has been carried out by a professional building company.

Anyway, the partnership with the students inside the community is becoming a shining example of how education, community involvement, and sustainability can intersect to create meaningful projects.

In September 2025, the orangery, the campfire hut and the tool shed, all built by the community from the demolished building recycled materials, have been officially inaugurated.

Involving local SMEs for a sustainable built environment

As part of the FÆLLESBO SUPERSHINE pilot project, FÆLLESBO is championing the reuse of building materials from renovation activities, a cornerstone of creating a sustainable built environment. Central to this effort is the exploration of which materials from the renovation of existing buildings can be effectively repurposed. This initiative is particularly significant given FÆLLESBO's ambitious plan to renovate approximately 2,000 of its 5,000 apartments, representing a substantial opportunity to rethink material use at scale.

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A critical element of this project is the collaboration with Næste, a local construction company specialising in building with reclaimed materials. Together, FÆLLESBO and Næste are conducting detailed inventories of salvaged wood from buildings slated for renovation. This process, undertaken by two FÆLLESBO staff members and two Næste specialists, involves identifying and categorising wood that holds potential for reuse, creating a specific know-how for the community with regards to sustainable construction materials.

Although the registration is still ongoing and data on the types and quantities of reusable wood is not yet available, this partnership highlights the vital role local businesses play in driving innovation in sustainable construction. By engaging Næste's expertise, FÆLLESBO not only accelerates its ability to identify practical solutions but also fosters a deeper understanding of sustainable materials within the local community.

Once the registration process is complete, FÆLLESBO will use the findings to create strategic plans for integrating salvaged wood into new construction projects. This approach not only reduces waste but also builds valuable know-how around sustainable building materials, empowering both the community and local businesses to contribute to a greener future. By prioritising local partnerships, FÆLLESBO demonstrates how collaboration can be a powerful tool for transforming the construction industry and embedding sustainability at the heart of the built environment.

Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding

FÆLLESBO has embarked on an ambitious plan to rewild shared green spaces, transforming traditional lawns into vibrant, diverse ecosystems. This shift presents challenges, not least in fostering enthusiasm among tenants for a landscape characterised by wild plants, more insects, and a natural aesthetic quite different from the neatly trimmed lawns they are accustomed to. Some tenants, particularly elder residents, may feel hesitant about these changes. Similarly, FÆLLESBO's operational staff, responsible for maintaining these areas, must adapt to new methods of care and receive training to manage wild spaces effectively.

Room for Difference initiative representatives

Another challenge lies in financing the transition. While reduced lawn maintenance might offer operational savings, substantial upfront investments are needed to establish and manage rewilded areas. FÆLLESBO is exploring whether these costs can be integrated into broader building renovation budgets, where green spaces are already slated for renewal.

To kickstart the initiative, FÆLLESBO organised an information and discussion session involving thirty tenants and thirty board members from various departments. The dialogue was aimed at gathering perspectives and proposals on rewilding possibilities.

Department 24 was chosen as the pilot area, and

FÆLLESBO sought funding from the Nordea Bank Fund to support the effort.

With the involvement of local stakeholders - including the housing-social initiative *Room for Difference*, Holtebjerg Childrenhouse, FGU Nature Line (a preparatory education programme), Herningsholm Public School, Youth School UngHerning, and Holtebjerg Activity House -, FÆLLESBO successfully secured approximately €140,000 for the pilot project.

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The next step was to engage Department 24's 270 tenants via a newsletter detailing the rewilding measures and funding opportunities. FÆLLESBO then hosted a meeting with ten local stakeholders, including municipal representatives, tenants, staff, environmental organisations, and local residents, to explore the project's possibilities. The group decided to begin the rewilding efforts by establishing raised plant beds. This activity brought together fifteen tenants, students from Herningsholm Business Academy, and a local entrepreneur to create the beds, marking a tangible first step in transforming the area.

FÆLLESBO has been encouraged by the strong interest and support from local stakeholders, the tenant board in Department 24, and the broader tenant community. The enthusiasm shown for the rewilding project is, in itself, a significant milestone, laying the groundwork for future initiatives. The results of this initial SUPERSHINE rewilding pilot will be carefully analysed to inform the planning and execution of subsequent activities. The insights gained will also help FÆLLESBO address barriers such as tenant hesitancy, operational challenges, and financial constraints. With the active involvement of tenants and local partners, FÆLLESBO is paving the way for a greener, more sustainable future while fostering community engagement and environmental stewardship.

Community-led sessions for identifying financing models for energy management technologies

FÆLLESBO has decided to install energy management systems with the aim of saving energy, increasing the share of renewable energy in the energy supply, and reducing energy costs for tenants. There is significant potential to achieve these benefits, thanks to the large share of cost-efficient renewable energy in the Danish energy system, which, through effective energy management, could cover a greater portion of electricity consumption. However, it is not possible to obtain attractive low-cost financing for the installation of these systems through conventional deep building renovation funding. Therefore, FÆLLESBO faces the challenge of identifying and testing appealing funding solutions for energy management systems.

The Neogrid PreHeat Energy Management System functioning process explained

As part of the SUPERSHINE pilot activity, FÆLLESBO aimed at identifying and, if possible, testing energy management systems through a participatory path with the tenants. As a first step, FÆLLESBO has involved several community stakeholders, meaning its own FÆLLESBO Handcraft department, the organisational board, the operational staff department, and external partners Danfoss and Neogrid Technologies, suppliers of energy management systems, along with an external energy expert. The goal was to identify the most suitable systems for FÆLLESBO.

In collaboration with Danfoss and Neogrid Technologies, FÆLLESBO has selected the Danfoss ECL and Neogrid Technologies PreHeat energy management systems, deemed appropriate for application and testing within the SUPERSHINE pilot activity. Following the testing phase, these

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systems will form the basis for further plans to install and operate energy management systems as part of the SUPERSHINE pilot activities. A key aspect of this process will be identifying attractive financing mechanisms for energy management systems, including the potential for crowd and ESCO financing models.

Training sessions on energy management technologies and PV systems

FÆLLESBO has identified the Danfoss ECL and Neogrid Technologies' Preheat systems as viable solutions for energy management. Recognising the importance of empowering their team, FÆLLESBO has embarked on a crucial journey to train both technical and administrative staff in the effective use of these systems. Three staff members from the FÆLLESBO Handcraft department and four from the administrative team are undergoing comprehensive training to apply the Danfoss ECL and Neogrid Preheat systems. The goal is to enable them to manage domestic water, heating, and ventilation systems efficiently, leading to significant energy savings.

This training initiative is not just a step in the SUPERSHINE pilot activity: it represents a fundamental part of FÆLLESBO's strategy to build a sustainable future. The importance of this training cannot be overstated, as it lays the foundation for FÆLLESBO to expand its use of energy management technologies. As staff become proficient in managing and maintaining these systems, FÆLLESBO will be able to implement and operate energy-saving technologies more effectively, reducing reliance on external support and fostering a long-term, self-sufficient approach to energy management. By equipping their staff with the knowledge and skills to operate these advanced energy management systems, FÆLLESBO aims at creating a self-sustaining model for system maintenance and operation, to be extended to the tenants' themselves later on, paving the road to the creation of new expertise and jobs.

In 2025, the training initiative has been extended to the management of the PV systems for the local staff.

Collaborative analysis on energy savings patterns and certificates

As part of its preparations for the broader implementation of energy management systems, FÆLLESBO is currently analysing its energy consumption data and energy certificates within the framework of the SUPERSHINE pilot activities, with support from the tenants themselves, providing pivotal insights on their energy consumption and savings patterns.

Lighting systems and facades

Furthermore, members of FÆLLESBO Department 200 board and four FÆLLESBO staff members, together with ESCO company SUSTAIN SOLUTIONS, are carrying out energy screening for four hundred and fifty households in Department 200 for energy saving measures implementation. This analysis is crucial for understanding the potential of applying energy management systems across its operations. However, the analysis is still ongoing, and no conclusions

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have yet been drawn regarding the specific opportunities for installing these systems.

The analysis was set to serve as a solid foundation for further planning and decision-making regarding the rollout of energy management systems. A key factor in this process was trying to identify the most suitable financing mechanisms, an essential step that FÆLLESBO aims to address through the SUPERSHINE pilot activity. Only by securing the right financial solutions can FÆLLESBO move forward with the implementation of these systems, ensuring their sustainability and effectiveness in reducing energy consumption.

Resident training with the local beekeepers' association on establishing and maintaining beehives

In the first quarter of 2025, residents participated in a practical training session led by the local beekeepers' association, which guided them through the process of setting up and maintaining beehives. The training covered the essential aspects of bee life cycles, hive management, sustainable practices to promote biodiversity, and honey harvesting. The practical sessions allowed participants to familiarise themselves with the tools and techniques involved, equipping them to manage the hives independently. Long-term maintenance practices were also discussed to ensure a healthy and productive apiary.

Birdhouses and insect hotels built together with the activity centre for elderly people and the daycare institution

From April 2025 onwards, two key groups (residents aged 60+ and children from the daycare institution) have been identified to support the construction of birdhouses and insect hotels using natural and sustainable materials. This intergenerational project

Residents looking at bee-keeping boxes

encouraged community engagement and promoted knowledge about local wildlife. During the activity, participants

learnt about different habitats for animals, fostering a richer biodiversity in our green oasis. These shelters provided small creatures and birds with safe havens, supporting their presence in our environment.

Walk and talk around the area for all project stakeholders and other interested residents

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In May 2025, the lighthouse manager organised a guided walk through the area for all SUPERSHINE stakeholders, including residents, community members, and other interested parties. During this walk, various ecological solutions implemented have been presented, such as the raised beds, wetland area, and biodiversity spaces. This was an opportunity to share progress, discuss challenges, and answer questions, fostering continued involvement and support from the local community.

Walk and talk through the area

Guided tour for the City Council of Herning Municipality in the area

In May 2025, SUPERSHINE organised a guided tour of the area for the Herning Municipality City Council. The purpose of this event was to showcase the benefits of the project and demonstrate how ecological solutions can enhance urban quality of life, promoting sustainability and biodiversity. The tour highlighted the most innovative aspects of the initiative, including green space management and practices that reduce the need for intensive maintenance. This meeting with local government representatives also helped to secure institutional support for the project and encourage its replication in other areas.

Residents discussing rewilding measures

Recruitment of volunteers to maintain the area, especially the raised beds, and to coordinate the rental of raised beds

In June 2025, FællesBo launched a recruitment campaign to find volunteers who can take care of the lighthouse green space, particularly the raised beds. Volunteers are planned to be in managing the rental system for the beds, which will allow residents to grow vegetables and flowers in their designated areas. This initiative is promoting a sense of ownership and care for the land, encouraging interaction between residents and strengthening the community.

Hiring of a local pocket-money worker to maintain the area together with the assigned property caretaker

From June 2025, the lighthouse hired a "pocket-money" worker, a local resident, to work alongside the designated property caretaker in maintaining the area. This scheme is providing a work opportunity for a local resident, while ensuring the ongoing upkeep of the green spaces. The worker has been appointed responsible for daily tasks such as plant care, cleaning communal areas, and managing resources, serving as a point of contact for the community.

Inauguration of the entire area with various activities and events

Foreseen by the end of 2025, the inauguration of the entire green space will be an opportunity to celebrate the completion of the project and officially present it to the community. Along with the department board of Dept. 24, FællesBo will organise events and activities that engage residents and visitors. There will be themed tours, environmental education workshops, social events, and other activities that highlight the importance of sustainability, biodiversity, and community involvement. The inauguration will also serve as a platform to stimulate new projects and future collaborations.

Community-shaped future vision of the Faellesbo district

The deep renovation measures undertaken by FÆLLESBO involve a comprehensive overhaul of the buildings structure. This includes insulating the walls, roofs, and floors, as well as replacing windows, doors, floors, and updating installations. Additionally, outdoor areas are being renovated to improve the overall environment around the building. These extensive renovation efforts are being financed through a combination of support from Landsbyggefonden and real estate loans, backed by municipal guarantees.

Render of a renovated apartment

The figure presents the render of a renovated apartment showcasing the transformation, reflecting the significant improvements made. The same can be said for the entire building, which, after renovation, stands as a testament to the potential for energy efficiency and aesthetic renewal (the render is shown in the below picture). The outdoor green spaces have also been revitalised, providing residents with a pleasant and sustainable environment.

Before the renovation, the building faced considerable challenges, including high heat consumption of 120 kWh/m² per year, compounded by issues with mould. However, following the renovation, it is expected that heat consumption will drop dramatically to just 37.0 kWh/m² per year, marking a significant achievement in energy efficiency and improved living conditions for the residents.

Render of an outdoor area among buildings

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2.1.2.1. Monitoring of SE KPIs

The measurement of Social Engagement indicators for the activities outlined in section 4.1.2 is presented in Table 2. These indicators provide a quantitative assessment of engagement at the demo site, supporting the implementation of the roadmap detailed in D1.2. The activities span the period related to the implementation of the roadmap. A distinguishing feature of FællesBo's engagement roadmap is the categorization of activities into four sub-groups: PV (photovoltaic), energy management, re-use of building materials, and re-wilding. In Table 2, each activity is identified by its corresponding sub-category, indicated in square brackets at the start of the description.

The KPI1.SE measurements reveal a high level of engagement overall, although about one-third of the activities did not meet the target number of participants. This data does not indicate a specific sub-category that consistently garners less interest from residents. However, the analysis on social acceptance reveals a persistent low awareness regarding solar energy initiatives, which could explain low levels of engagement. Additionally, KPI2.SE measurements confirm that all key stakeholder groups were effectively reached through the activities. Furthermore, the sole capacity-building initiative, "Training sessions on energy management technologies," successfully engaged all targeted participants.

Table 2: Social Engagement Indicators for FællesBo demo site

KPI code and name	Stakeholder Outreach (KPI1.SE)	Stakeholders Groups (KPI2.SE)	Capacity building activities (KPI4.SE)
KPI definition	This KPI measures the number of stakeholders engaged in the LH for each activity conducted (e.g., co-design sessions, capacity building sessions, community events) according to the target set	This KPI assesses the participation of all stakeholders' groups that the activity aims to engage in the event. For instance, if a workshop involving tenants, students and local association has been planned, it is important to verify that all stakeholders' groups have participated.	Number of SHs reached by capacity building activities or material prepared
Unit of measurement	%	%	Number
Engagement activity 1: Questionnaire-focused meeting (11 members of FB organization board)	(8 participants / 11 target) = 73%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 2: Questionnaire-focused meeting (Director and project of FB)	(2 participants / 2 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	n/a

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Engagement activity 3 [PV]: PV systems pilot installation validation and co-decision meeting	(13 participants / 20 target) = 65%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 4 [PV]: Stakeholders' dialogue for financing PV systems	(49 participants / 40 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 5 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Stakeholder-led administrative sessions for the construction of an orangery	(35 participants / 35 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 6 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Regular meetings to involve students from the Herningsholm Business Academy	(35 participants / 35 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 7 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Community-led building of a garden shed and a fireplace	(40 participants / 40 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 8 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Involving local SMEs for a sustainable built environment	(4 participants / 4 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 9 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (Information and discussion about increasing bio-diversity in common green areas)	(30 participants / 25 target) = 83%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 10 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (By re-wilding increasing bio-diversity in FB department 24's green common areas)	(270 participants / 270 target) = 100%	(1 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>

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Engagement activity 11 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (Up-start meeting for preparing the re-wilding project in FB department 24)	(10 participants / 8 target) = 80%	(5 SH categories participated / 5 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 12 [RE-WILDING]: Tenants' awareness raising meetings about rewilding (Building raised plant beds in FB department 24)	(15 participants / 15 target) = 100%	(4 SH categories participated / 4 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 13 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT] Community-led sessions for identifying financing models for energy management technologies	(5 participants / 7 target) = 71%	(5 SH categories participated / 6 target SH) = 83%	n/a
Engagement activity 14 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT]: Training sessions on energy management technologies	(7 participants / 7 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	7
Engagement activity 15 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT]: Collaborative analysis on energy savings patterns and certificates	(7 participants / 7 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 16 [PV]: Training of staff	(4 participants / 20 target) = 20%	(2 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 200%	2
Engagement activity 17 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT]: Start-up meeting, Implementation plan for ECL energy management	(6 participants / 7 target) = 85%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	n/a
Engagement activity 18 [ENERGY MANAGEMENT]: Start-up meeting, Implementation plan for ECL energy management	(20 participants / 7 target) = 285%	(12 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 500%	n/a
Engagement activity 19 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Large meeting	(20 participants / 40 target) = 50%	(5 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 250%	n/a

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with all volunteers in the Oase project			
Engagement activity 20 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Event for residents “while we wait for the area to be completed” in Holtbjerg	(25 participants / 40 target) = 62%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 21 [RE-USE OF BUILDING MATERIALS]: Inauguration of orangery, campfire hut and tool shed made of recycled materials	(35 participants / 35 target) = 100%	(5 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 250%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 22 [URBAN REFORESTATION]: Theme day on energy optimization and biodiversity for all FællesBos employees	(100 participants / 270 target) = 37%	(2 SH categories participated / 4 target SH) = 50%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 23 [URBAN REFORESTATION]: Big meeting with all volunteers in the Oase project	(20 participants / 15 target) = 133%	(5 SH categories participated / 5 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 24 [URBAN REFORESTATION]: Event for residents “while we wait for the area to be completed” in Holtbjerg	(25 participants / 25 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 250%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 25 [URBAN REFORESTATION]: Inauguration of orangery, campfire hut and tool shed made of recycled materials	(35 participants / 25 target) = 140%	(7 SH categories participated / 1 target SH) = 700%	<i>n/a</i>
Engagement activity 26 [GENERAL FOR ALL]: Event sustainability strategy for the organization board facilitated by Bæredygtig Herning	(15 participants / 15 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%	<i>n/a</i>

2.1.3. Trieste – Italy

Context overview and engagement roadmap summary

As described in details in D1.1, D1.2, and D1.3, the SUPERSHINE lighthouse of Trieste is

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embedded within a socio-economic landscape that has long been characterised by significant concentrations of social housing and a pressing need for renewal. The Boito district, in particular, epitomises these challenges, with outdated housing stock, limited access to energy-efficient systems, and a demographic profile shaped largely by households from economically disadvantaged groups. For these residents, daily comfort and immediate well-being often outweighed long-term sustainability objectives, leading to ATER decision to demolish the old complex and rebuilt it entirely, with an architectural and urban planning project that has been object of validation and integration by the community. Mistrust towards public initiatives, rooted in a history of insufficient transparency in housing projects, has further underscored the importance of building confidence and ownership among future tenants. Against this backdrop, the renovation project in Trieste is conceived not simply as an exercise in demolition and reconstruction, but as an ambitious effort to dismantle both physical and social barriers, transforming Boito into a more open, inclusive, and sustainable neighbourhood. Investments extend beyond the replacement of building envelopes and the installation of renewable energy technologies, such as rooftop photovoltaics and heat recovery systems. They are equally directed at upgrading road networks, public utilities, parking spaces, and green areas, thereby reconnecting the district with its surroundings and enhancing liveability for current and future generations.

This transformative approach is firmly anchored in Trieste's long-standing "Habitat-Microareas" Programme, a collaborative initiative launched in 1998 by the Municipality, ATER Trieste, and local health and social actors. Initially targeted at ATER tenants, and later extended to surrounding communities, the programme has become a cornerstone of local welfare, blending healthcare, education, housing, and civic participation in line with European social policy frameworks. Today, the 14 Microarea centres, each with a Social Concierge desk, act as vital neighbourhood hubs, offering not only social and health assistance but also opportunities for community-building through shared events, libraries, and support services for vulnerable groups. This infrastructure of trust and proximity provides a fertile ground for SUPERSHINE's participatory model, enabling residents to play an active role in shaping their living environments while strengthening solidarity and social cohesion.

The Trieste engagement roadmap was articulated by ICONS through five sequential phases. The first, **Awareness and Engagement**, introduced the community to the project through a kick-off social event to introduce the objectives, the renovation plan developed by ATER, and the intended pathway for co-design activities. The second, the **Design Phase**, involved participatory workshops and questionnaires to define the future district, covering aspects such as aesthetics, green spaces, mobility, and services. The co-design process has not only relied on meetings and workshops, but has also been anchored in the creation of a tangible point of reference: indeed, in May 2025, ATER, in collaboration with Kallipolis APS, set up a housing module in Via Boito to serve as a physical Hub for the established **SUPERSHINE Living Lab**. The third, the **Renovation Phase**, is accompanying the finalised (and updated with community inputs) architectural and urban planning project towards the start of the construction work in the upcoming years. This has been carried out, at first, with an evaluation questionnaire for the co-design process in Summer 2025, and, in September 2025, with a conclusive meeting presenting the co-design results: the process will continue, in the final months of 2025, leveraging on the established SUPERSHINE Living Lab with a plan for training programmes and transparent communication channels to familiarise tenants with new technologies and spaces, as well as preparing the future opportunities for green and maintenance jobs in the new complex. The fourth, the **Transition Phase**, will carry on the legacy of the project from 2026 onwards, celebrating the completion of works through neighbourhood events and community-building workshops, strengthening the established cohesion and a sense of belonging. Finally, the **Monitoring and Continuity Phase**, will ensure long-term sustainability through the creation of an advisory group to bring bottom-up participation towards co-decision for the future of the Boito

District.

In this way, the lighthouse of Trieste demonstrates how technical innovation, urban redevelopment, and participatory governance can converge to redefine social housing as both a material asset and a living ecosystem. By situating the refurbishment within the city's broader microarea framework, SUPERSHINE not only addresses immediate housing needs but also contributes to building a more equitable and resilient urban fabric, where residents are empowered as co-creators of their shared future.

Co-design for Social Housing refurbishment in Boito: an overview of the framework

The adopted methodology has been rooted in participatory design, applied to the formulation and implementation of *people-centred* local development policies, using facilitation tools such as

Map of the Boito district with the lighthouse area and the neighbouring area

engagement, listening, co-design, and empowerment. The pathway implemented in the Trieste lighthouse aimed at co-designing the new ATER Residential Complex of Via Boito, through not only community-led validation of the ATER architectural and urban planning project for the new social housing residential complex of Via Boito, but also its detailed integration with a vision for collective spaces and desired services in the surrounding area, engaging specific target groups. This approach made it possible to identify the needs and aspirations of different categories of residents more precisely and concretely. To encourage participation, meetings have been promoted among residents through personal invitations, word-of-

mouth among neighbours, and engagement with local stakeholders, supported by dedicated informational materials distributed within the neighbourhood, at public facilities, and in local businesses. Among these, "Bar Latteria Antonella" has emerged as a key point of reference, thanks to the support of its owner, who has facilitated the dissemination of project initiatives. Furthermore, in May 2025, ATER Trieste, in collaboration with Kallipolis APS, set up a housing module in Via Boito to serve as a recognisable landmark in the neighbourhood. While awaiting the start of construction, it was used as a living lab for two meetings on public spaces for collective use.

The preparatory phase of the project involved constructing the territorial context through stakeholder mapping. This analysis identified key informants and participants to be involved in the participatory pathway. The mapping activity is dynamic and inclusive, aiming to engage institutions and groups, including informal ones, that hold relevant perspectives on the issues being addressed. Furthermore, stakeholder mapping helped monitor which local actors need to be included to ensure the project's development is as comprehensive and integrated as possible. Through these actions, the project positioned itself not only as an urban intervention but also as an opportunity to strengthen the sense of community and promote an active participation model that values every voice and perspective.

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The community engagement activities for co-creation and co-design towards the Boito district renovation followed the designed project strategy and roadmap, provided by ICONS, and directly integrated by ATER with insights from BOITO's needs and wants.

Engagement timeline

Kick-off and launch of the activities

The kick-off event in Boito

On 13 June 2024, the launch event of co-design activities was organised with the presence of the community. The institutions and all the stakeholders involved have been presented by ATER, supported by APRE, with the path that will be followed in the upcoming months to maximise the engagement and the direct involvement of the stakeholders, as well as the survey questionnaire to be administered to the population. The redevelopment project of the complex was outlined and presented to the community during the kick-off event, obtaining appreciation from the institutions, trade and professional associations and companies present at the meeting. This event represented a pivotal moment for

connecting with residents was the public presentation of the participatory pathway, as some residents volunteered to inform and invite others within their networks of contacts.

Questionnaire data collection sessions with the community

The questionnaire data collection activities began in July 2024, and was completed by September 2024. For the facilitation of co-design processes on the territory, ATER is being supported by social experts from the Association for Social Promotion 'Kallipolis'.

The co-design activities implementation

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The co-design activities, that have been practically implemented from September 2024 to May 2025, have been planned in detail to be dedicated to the different population targets, also including younger segments of the local population, and have been followed by a general meeting to return the results, in the presence of all the stakeholders involved in the project.

As a starting point, co-creation sessions have been activated with a focus on the external appearance of buildings, green areas and public spaces, in particular:

- Presenting the engagement roadmap for Trieste*
- Adult target: 1 meeting dedicated to all citizens, 1 meeting dedicated to resident girls and women.
 - Youth target: 1 meeting dedicated to the age group 8-11, 1 meeting dedicated to the age group 12-20.
 - Adult target: 1 meeting dedicated to possible beneficiaries of the Microarea, meaning the specific denomination urbanistically given to the district of Boito, with its own peculiarities.
 - A co-design session on neighbourhood services will also be activated, with the purpose of “the 15 minutes city”, meaning a plan to transform the connections (not only transportation) inside the neighbourhood in a more efficient and human-centred way.
 - Adult target: 1 meeting dedicated to all citizens.

Co-design sessions for future services in the Microarea of Boito

A shot from one of the co-design sessions

In October 2024, SUPERSHINE hosted two engaging co-design sessions for the future services to be implemented in the Microarea of Boito, aimed at fostering collaboration and idea generation among key stakeholders. The first session brought together service providers from neighbouring Microareas, targeting professionals who are already involved in the local ecosystem. The second meeting focused on social gatekeepers, inviting service referents who act as vital intermediaries within the community network.

Both sessions commenced with a comprehensive presentation of the project's goals and the participatory pathway by representatives from

ATER Trieste and the facilitators from the association for social promotion Kallipolis APS. These introductions set the stage for collaborative discussions that would unfold over the next two hours. The brainstorming sessions, guided by experienced facilitators, encouraged participants to explore

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A SWOT analysis board from the event

key themes and challenges. Stimulus questions were employed to spark conversations and foster collective reasoning, ensuring that the discussions remained both focused and dynamic.

The primary aim of these sessions was to develop a SWOT analysis and gather innovative ideas for new services that the Microarea initiative could offer to its neighbourhoods. The SWOT analysis served as a strategic tool, shedding light on the intervention's characteristics and its interplay with the surrounding environment. By examining internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) alongside external ones (opportunities and threats), participants were able to align their strategies with achievable objectives. This methodology proved invaluable in identifying controllable variables within the project while also recognising external factors that, although beyond the organisation's direct influence, could be managed or leveraged. By doing so, the team aimed to amplify positive outcomes while mitigating risks that could hinder the initiative's success. The sessions exemplified a structured yet creative approach to participatory planning, paving the way for practical and impactful innovations in community service delivery.

innovations in community service delivery.

INTERNAL VARIABLES	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Settlement of New Inhabitants (60 apartments for a total of about 180 inhabitants) - Construction of the new Microarea Headquarters on the ground floor (<u>Presidio habitat microarea</u>) - Presence of Neighborhood Services - Presence of a police station - Opening of the public spaces of the new housing complex to the entire neighborhood - Realization of green facades that will contribute to the "urban status" of the neighborhood and bring beauty - Realization of large multifunctional spaces (community kitchen, theater-cinema, library) - Attention to accessibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing establishments have been empty for a long time - Failure of tenants to comply with ATER regulations. - inhabitants target of ATER houses have little care for communal spaces - Lack of sense of belonging to the neighborhood since the settlement of new residents will go by ATER rankings - High dropout rate - Difficulty in maintaining the beauty
EXTERNAL VARIABLES	

Opportunities	Risk (threats)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activation of projects based on the Public-Private Partnership for the management of services - Establishment of a neighborhood board and/or resident committees linked to house numbers - realization of aggregation services for the elderly - realization of a neighborhood library and/or toy library - presence of educational and school services - Presence of services for sports activities - focus intervention for children and young people with an entertainment service for young children to support family management - Reclaiming the neighborhood soccer field - Connection with the Chamber of Commerce Project aimed at encouraging services' activation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New residents will be selected based on the ATER Ranking and therefore cannot be involved in the participatory pathway phase - The Law Enforcement Presidium with the presence of the barracks may hinder the aggregation of the neighborhood, also because of the service that will be activated to dispense the residence permit - Disillusionment of citizens by not delivering what was promised or delivering it in too long a time frame - Resistance on the part of the municipality to promote innovative services - During the uncovered hours of social and educational services, it can be difficult to handle some distressing situations typical of public housing neighborhoods - The figure of the "Head of Household" as representative of the condominium may generate situations of conflict or excessive individualism instead of facilitating the ATER-tenant relationship - The lack of the "family of origin context" can be an impediment to the integration of new tenants - The economic scarcity of families residing in the new complex can be an obstacle to the care and maintenance of the spaces.

Regarding the surfacing of new ideas, the stimulus question posed was:

“What services and spaces are needed to improve the social cohesion and community health of residents through the construction of the ATER Trieste complex in Via Boito?”

The following are the contributions that emerged.

A suggestions board from one of the events

<p>Organization of residents' groups forco-management of public spaces</p>	<p>The possibility of supporting the organization of inhabitant groups to promote the co-management of commonspaces in the new ATER complex could promote and realize:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the activation of a Community Kitchen as a laboratory for experimentation and sociability - the takeover of green care - the good management of pets and domestic animals
<p>Public spaces and services</p>	<p>The request for improvement of publicsplaces and services concerns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintaining and activating dedicated food services - implementing a playground - Maintain and improve public transportation service to the city center (Buses) - Provide several water points (drinking fountains) - Ensuring adequate lighting
<p>Social hub and service “Habitat Microarea”</p>	<p>Suburban neighborhoods need beautiful and welcoming gathering spaces that can also contain innovative services that will also attract citizens living in the city center. Among these we call for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the creation of a public gathering space for the neighborhood such as the “<u>Square</u>” - The activation of a play space both outdoors and indoors such as a toy library dedicated to children, young people but also adults - A free and flexible gathering space both outdoors and indoors, suitable for all ages - the possibility of activating a neighborhood library - enhancement of the after-schoolservice

Elements also emerge that can be considered to cut across all proposals:

- *Intergenerationality*: new spaces and services must be able to meet the needs of children, young people and the elderly.
- *Beauty*: spaces must be of quality and with a focus on design and its forms (i.e., the opposite of the spaces often found in Trieste's predominantly public housing suburbs)

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- **Colour and art:** the new ATER complex must be able to recall the importance of colour, as an antithesis to grey, the colour of concrete symbolizing decay and suburban life, and art that can express itself in different ways and that can also involve the new inhabitants.

A journey through the neighbourhood: an exploratory walk for community engagement

On a bright Saturday morning of October, an exploratory walk unfolded in the heart of the neighbourhood. This participatory event was designed to bring together residents, stakeholders, and citizens in a shared journey of discovery. Organised with the support of representatives from ATER TS and Kallipolis APS, the walk promised not only insights into the area but also a chance to foster connections among those who call it home.

Leading the group was Mr. Mario Sorz, a long-time resident and devoted historian of the neighbourhood. With his enthusiasm and knowledge, he guided the participants along a thoughtfully planned route, beginning at Via Boito. From there, the group ventured down Via Puccini, visiting landmarks such as the municipal kindergarten "Azzurra," the elementary school G. Foschiatti, the serene Marisa Madieri municipal garden, and the parish church of Jesus Divine Worker. The journey continued, retracing Via Boito to explore the District 3 headquarters of the Azienda Sanitaria, the Acquerello kindergarten on Via Puccini, and finally returning to the Antonella Dairy Bar, where refreshments awaited.

A journey through the neighbourhood event pictures

Walking, in this context, served as more than just a mode of transportation. It became a tool for connection and reflection. As the group meandered through the streets, a natural rhythm of conversation emerged. Participants shared observations, posed questions, expressed wishes, and swapped anecdotes about the neighbourhood's history. These informal exchanges brought to light a tapestry of experiences, memories, and ideas, creating a vibrant narrative of the area's identity and potential.

This approach not only strengthened bonds among the participants but also deepened their understanding of the neighbourhood and the proposed projects on the horizon. Through this shared exploration, a sense of community and collaboration flourished. The participants articulated several aspirations and concerns, which underscored the importance of thoughtful redevelopment:

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- **Revitalising spaces:** There was a clear call for both outdoor and indoor spaces to foster social interaction across all age groups.
- **Enhancing green areas:** The need for communal green spaces where children could play safely, free from the dangers of traffic, was strongly voiced.
- **Preserving essential services:** Many emphasised the importance of maintaining and expanding local services to prevent the neighbourhood from becoming a dormitory zone.
- **Encouraging innovation:** Participants envisioned aesthetically pleasing, innovative spaces designed to facilitate community gatherings.

In essence, the walk was more than just a stroll through familiar streets. It was a step towards a collective vision, a dialogue on how to preserve and enhance the neighbourhood while ensuring it remains a vibrant and inclusive space for all.

Other shots of the day

Co-design sessions for younger population: first workshop

Arch. Cechet showing the project for the new ATER complex in Via Boito to children

On January the 13th 2025, a dedicated session aimed at engaging younger participants was held, employing the *Block by Block* methodology developed by the United Nations agency UN-Habitat. This methodology utilises the popular video game *Minecraft* as a virtual modelling tool for the co-design of project proposals in collaboration with young people. The use of games and video games as participatory tools is intended to facilitate self-expression and support the transition from conceptual ideas to concrete designs, effectively transforming the needs and aspirations of participants into tangible actions.

Minecraft is among the most widely played computer games globally. It enables users to interact with a three-dimensional digital environment by placing different types of coloured blocks (similar to "digital Lego") to construct buildings, landscapes, and entire urban settings. It can be played in both multiplayer and single-player modes. Its creative mode allows for the intuitive creation of complex structures, similar to those produced using advanced 3D modelling software, with the added benefit of

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collaborative functionality through multiplayer features.

A number of case studies demonstrate that the game enhances young people's interest in urban planning and design, enabling them to express their ideas visually while also fostering the development of key skills and encouraging community networking. Designing in *Minecraft* allows young participants to explore alternative design solutions and visualise their ideas; it serves as a platform to examine and question different perspectives. The deliberative process further supports the development of a more comprehensive understanding of the urban environment, greater public speaking confidence, and the strengthening of social relationships².

Minecraft modelling

The session took place at the premises of Edilmaster – La scuola edile di Trieste (Trieste Building School), which provided both the classroom and the necessary computer equipment as part of its ongoing collaboration with ATER Trieste and the local community. Participants were boys and girls from the Cobolli recreation centre, which primarily serves young people from the nearby Foschiatti school (an institution closely linked to the neighbourhood).

The two-hour session commenced with a presentation outlining the project objectives and the participatory process, delivered by representatives of ATER Trieste and facilitators from the Association for Social Promotion Kallipolis. Following this, using brainstorming techniques, the facilitators guided participants in reflecting on the elements and activities they would wish to find and experience in a space intended for collective use.

Other shots of the day (not showing children's face for privacy)

The ideas proposed encompassed a broad spectrum of topics: infrastructure to support sustainable mobility, design guidelines for new buildings, furnishings for green public spaces, and new services for the neighbourhood. The young participants envisaged an extension of the existing neighbourhood, linked to the city centre by a **dedicated cycle path**.

² The information provided here is freely taken from the report *Using Minecraft For Youth Participation in Urban Design and Governance*, UN-Habitat. For further information on the use of Minecraft in participatory spatial planning processes and youth engagement, see: <https://unhabitat.org/using-minecraft-for-youth-participation-in-urban-design-and-governance>

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A significant emphasis was placed on the need for **high-quality green spaces**: specifically, a park with newly planted vegetation, picnic tables with shelters and gazebos, relaxation areas with drinking fountains and recycling facilities. The park was also to include a play area with equipment suitable for various age groups, such as swings and slides. Furthermore, there was a strong desire for spaces dedicated to communal sports activities, including a basketball court, tennis courts, a football pitch, a golf course, a skating rink, and a dedicated area for skateboarding.

In the envisioned new areas, participants also expressed interest in having spaces for themed workshops (including cosplay and comic-related activities), a reasonably priced café, and an open-air theatre suitable for hosting **small concerts**.

The discussion subsequently shifted towards the architectural scale of the project, focusing on the appearance and functionality of future buildings. These were imagined as five-storey structures with light-coloured façades. Each flat should have no fewer than five windows and include a spacious kitchen. A further essential requirement identified by participants was the provision of significantly more parking spaces than are currently available.

The final stage of the session involved the modelling phase using *Minecraft*, during which the various groups developed the aspects of the environment they found most engaging. The session concluded with presentations by each group, showcasing their work.

Co-design sessions for younger population: second ‘design thinking’ workshop

Children graphically expressing their wishes for the neighbourhood

The second co-design session specifically tailored for younger participants took place on January the 20th 2025 at the Cobolli recreation centre in Trieste. On this occasion, the *design thinking* methodology was employed, which is based on the principles of a *human-centred approach*. This approach begins with an understanding of individuals' needs in order to develop innovative solutions that directly respond to those needs.

Following a brief introduction to the project, participants were provided with a *Personas Canvas Users* form, through which they were invited to imagine a potential user of the project area and describe some of their characteristics. This exercise enabled participants to articulate their needs and aspirations regarding the design and use of public space.

The working methodology involved an initial individual task in which participants completed the form, responding (both in written and graphical form) to the question: **"What would you like to find in the new neighbourhood of Via Boito?"**.

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The majority of participants expressed a strong desire for a **park featuring a wooded area and equipped spaces with benches and tables**, where they could enjoy picnics or snacks with friends. They also highlighted the importance of drinking fountains and bins with lids placed throughout the park. Within the park, they envisioned play areas with swings, slides, sandpits for building sandcastles, interactive statues, and multi-purpose spaces suitable for various games. Areas dedicated to skateboarding, cycling paths, and parkour circuits were also frequently mentioned. Some participants expressed enthusiasm for the idea of a permanent amusement park nearby.

Children with the model for the new Boito complex

Additionally, the park was envisioned as offering practical services such as a **café, rental facilities for bicycles and electric scooters (for both adults and children), and a games room.**

Among the more seasonal ideas that emerged was a proposal for the Christmas

period: decorating the streets with festive lights and inflatable figures, and organising a community walk to Piazza Unità while singing Christmas carols.

Following the plenary sharing of the imagined user profiles and their respective characteristics, the session progressed to the prototyping phase. This phase supports a creative transition from conceptual thinking to tangible design. Working in small groups, participants created models of the desired elements to be included in the future space, using a variety of materials provided, such as modelling clay, newspaper cuttings, and cardboard.

Notably, the group work resulted in the development of imaginative **prototypes of buildings conceived by the children, characterised by green roofs and façades.**

The prominent presence of trees and vegetation was identified as a defining element of the new neighbourhood, extending even into its architectural features. The session concluded with a collective sharing of all the prototypes among the participants.

ATER and Kallipolis managing the activity

Co-design sessions for residents: first workshop ‘Public spaces... designed together!’

The new SUPERSHINE housing module for community co-creation

The first workshop hosted by the SUPERSHINE housing module was held on May the 6th 2025: it was dedicated to families and local residents centred around the theme “*A Neighbourhood of Proximity: The Challenge of the 15-Minute City.*” The two-hour session began with a presentation of the project’s objectives by representatives of ATER Trieste, followed by an introduction to the concept of the 15-minute city by facilitators from Kallipolis APS. This concept, which focuses on proximity, was discussed in relation to local services and public spaces intended for shared use.

To initiate engagement, participants were asked to reflect on the aspects of the neighbourhood they currently appreciate, dislike, or wish to see introduced. During this initial phase, participants highlighted the neighbourhood’s sense of “isolation,” largely attributed to the presence of a major thoroughfare (Via Flavia), which acts as a barrier separating it from the adjacent district of Giarizzole. Furthermore, the Via Boito complex is perceived as disconnected from Via Catalani, and its topography creates a sense of detachment from the lower Maddalena district. The lack (and at times misuse) of green spaces was also noted, alongside a general shortage of communal gathering places. Notably, the area’s tranquillity was not viewed positively, as it was associated with the absence of key services, including an ATER concierge service, a civic centre, local shops, and a newsagent.

Among the appreciated elements, participants pointed to the presence of a historic healthcare facility within the neighbourhood. A petition had been launched in an effort to prevent its closure, underlining its importance to the community. In envisioning future developments, participants expressed a desire for the introduction of a library, informal gathering places, and dedicated spaces for young people. The group was then encouraged to consider what services are essential for a neighbourhood to function effectively on a daily basis.

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Image from the session

The methodology employed during this phase was *Inquiry by Design*, supported by a physical model of the area produced by two trainees from Edilmaster – La scuola edile di Trieste (Trieste Building School). Beginning with green spaces, the discussion underscored the importance of regular maintenance, identified as a key responsibility of ATER. Nonetheless, it was also suggested that residents could play an active role in this process through participatory projects, such as the *Ri-giardino* initiative.

With regard to local services, participants expressed a preference for the introduction of small, locally operated

shops (ideally run by social cooperatives), with support from the local authority. This was seen as a balanced alternative to the current overabundance of supermarkets in the area. As for collective spaces, participants stressed that these should be publicly owned and designed for both recreational and sporting purposes. Suggestions included sports fields, a rock climbing wall, outdoor fitness equipment, well-equipped walking trails, and a covered, well-lit open space to serve as a social hub for young people.

Indoor spaces, which should also house the *Microarea* services, were envisioned as open and shared environments. These could foster new partnerships with local residents and voluntary associations. Proposals included multifunctional facilities incorporating co-working spaces, a rehearsal room for young people, a large venue for theatrical performances, and a kitchen for hosting community meals and social events.

Physical model of the Boito area

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Additionally, in order to rebuild a sense of community among residents, participants proposed developing a support programme focused on cohabitation, with a view to experimenting with solidarity-based living arrangements, particularly for younger people. The session also featured the participation of an illustrator, who used the technique of *graphic recording* to help participants visually capture and reflect on the key ideas that emerged throughout the discussion.

Co-design sessions for residents: second workshop ‘Public spaces...for girls, for everyone!’

The second workshop, held on May the 27th 2025, was a two-hour session specifically tailored for young girls and women, with a clear focus on adopting **a gender perspective in the analysis and design of urban spaces**. This approach wanted to explore whether a gender perspective towards future renovations could make a difference for women. With the session, SUPERSHINE moved beyond a gender-neutral perspective, actively recognising how specific interventions can empower local women, by integrating their desires and needs for services, recreation, proximity, and safety. Thus, SUPERSHINE aimed at ensuring that the new Boito district developments consider the differing needs of women and men in terms of community integration, access to local amenities, and security.

The session began with a presentation of the project objectives by representatives from ATER Trieste, followed by an introduction from the facilitators of Kallipolis APS on the theme of proximity, specifically in relation to public services and shared spaces. The session employed the methodology of gender-based analysis to guide the discussion and proposals. The workshop commenced with the construction of a *problem tree*, with the central issue identified as the frequent inadequacy of public spaces in meeting the needs of girls and women.

The problem tree being populated

In analysing the neighbourhood, participants first examined the root causes of this issue. It emerged that the topographical differences in the area contribute to fragmented and poorly connected spaces, limiting accessibility. The peripheral nature of the neighbourhood, along with the relocation of many families and young people, has led to a significant reduction in green areas, seating, play spaces, and local shops.

Additional causes identified included bureaucratic delays and a lack of engagement by political representatives, both of which serve to reinforce the current state of underdevelopment. The perceived effects of these conditions include a sense of insecurity and a broader atmosphere of neglect, stemming from long-standing inaction in the area.

Participants were then invited to identify possible actions for

Participants were then invited to identify possible actions for

The impact-effort matrix

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improvement and assess them using an *impact-effort matrix*, evaluating both feasibility and potential effect. Most of the proposed actions were deemed easy or moderately easy to implement, with the likelihood of generating medium to high impact.

Drafting the inputs to integrate the plan

Regarding outdoor spaces, participants proposed improved pedestrian connectivity throughout the neighbourhood, the introduction of play areas featuring table tennis tables with mobile phone charging stations, more inviting and functional street furniture, and the provision of at least one clean, accessible, and aesthetically pleasing public toilet.

There was also a strong desire for the establishment of an *open micro-area*, imagined as a multifunctional community hub. This space would include a library, a games room, a party room, baby changing facilities, and a dedicated meeting space for women to engage in activities such as sewing and crafts.

Among the more complex, yet high-impact, proposals were the creation of a physiotherapy centre or polyclinic, and the establishment of a women-focused commercial space (e.g., a gym or spa), operated through private initiative.

Co-design session with social group, representatives and educators from the Giarizzole Microarea service

As part of the ongoing co-design process, a dedicated one-hour session was held with adult participants (specifically, members of the social group as well as representatives and educators from the *Giarizzole Microarea* service). The session aimed at exploring current community activities, assess unmet needs, and gather ideas for future initiatives.

What the Microarea brings to people according to the community

The Microarea also offers practical support, such as assistance with job-seeking through work grant programmes.

The session began with a presentation of the project's objectives by representatives from ATER Trieste. This was followed by a facilitated brainstorming exercise led by Kallipolis APS, during which participants were invited to reflect on their favourite activities currently offered by the Microarea, the needs these activities address, and additional opportunities for community engagement.

Participants unanimously emphasised the importance of the Microarea as a place of **solidarity and companionship**. It is perceived not merely as a service, but as an extended family, a space where individuals are encouraged to participate in activities they might not undertake alone. The

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A key element that fosters connection among community members is **shared meals**. Communal lunches, cooking workshops (e.g. homemade pasta and gnocchi), informal snacks, and themed neighbourhood parties (e.g., the "shooting star party" featuring barbecues and karaoke), were all highlighted as powerful tools for building social bonds and mutual understanding.

Organised **group outings by minibus** also play a significant role in strengthening the community. Excursions led by experts, cultural visits to exhibitions, seaside trips, and theatre or cinema outings were cited as valuable experiences that deepen relationships within the group and promote mobility between neighbouring Microareas. These outings were seen as a service with the potential to coordinate and connect multiple community events. Accordingly, participants stressed the need for a transport service accessible to individuals with limited mobility.

Creative and artistic activities are also greatly appreciated, not only for their aesthetic appeal but for their potential to inspire take-home projects, such as the "Colour at Home" initiative. These activities can enhance both individual well-being and the shared atmosphere during communal events.

Image from the session

Participants also expressed a clear **need for larger, flexible spaces**, ideally co-managed by residents. One proposal involved establishing a **shared library**, created through book donations from families and individuals, with the aim of making it a local hub for families. The ground floor of the building in Via Flavia was suggested as a suitable location for this initiative. The space could be jointly managed by residents in collaboration with the Microarea, reinforcing a sense of ownership and community responsibility.

Finally, the discussion extended to **public spaces**, with participants envisioning accessible pavements leading to shaded, comfortable areas furnished with benches and drinking fountains, welcoming environments where people can sit, read, and relax beneath trees. The possibility of creating **shared vegetable gardens** was also raised as a way to promote sustainability and social interaction.

Future vision of the Boito district

Overview of the New ATER Residential Complex in Via Boito (Render, Map)

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As aforementioned, ATER Trieste plans to demolish and rebuild the buildings in the district of Boito, to overcome their functional obsolescence, their state of deterioration, as well as the technological inadequacy, with an organic series of redevelopment and renovation interventions, co-created with the neighbouring communities and the local Association for Social Promotion 'Kallipolis' as facilitator.

The architectural and urban planning project of the new ATER residential complex in Via Boito is set to redefine sustainable living with its innovative design and focus on energy efficiency. Comprised of seven modern buildings, it introduces fifty-six additional apartments tailored to contemporary lifestyles. Each structure is equipped with advanced energy-saving technologies, including photovoltaic panels that harness clean energy and systems for heat recovery, ensuring minimal environmental impact. Dedicated parking spaces are also included.

Residents will benefit from a range of collective amenities, including accessible and equipped association spaces and vibrant green recreational areas. Urban and vertical gardens bring nature closer, while water recovery systems and blue-green roofs enhance ecological resilience. Designed with acoustic comfort in mind, the complex provides a peaceful living environment amidst the hustle of city life.

On the ground floor, the complex will provide the community with premises for various uses, primarily commercial: indeed, during the engagement pathway, many residents of the Boito district have expressed interest in opening businesses in the new complex, which is therefore also addressing the lack of suitable space for this purpose.

Green Houses classes A0 & A+

Community inputs were particularly significant in extending the vision of the new complex, going beyond the mere buildings to shape common spaces as well: in fact, the ATER architectural and urban planning project is now including the upgrading of road networks, public utilities, parking spaces, and green areas to reconnect the Boito district with the surrounding areas, seeking to overcome the geographic isolation perceived by the residents of the previous complex. The project places emphasis on accessibility for all residents, including those with limited mobility, in line with the broader Habitat Microareas framework.

Render of one of the future buildings in Boito

This ambitious project also opens the door to the creation of an energy community, empowering residents to share and manage resources sustainably. It is a vision of modern living where innovation meets environmental responsibility.

Road map of the area, with new interconnections planned in the new ATER Plan

2.1.3.1. Monitoring of SE KPIs

Table 3 below presents the Social Engagement indicators measured for all the activities in Trieste described in section 4.1.3. The table is referred to all the phases of the roadmap.

Participation levels were consistently high, with the kick-off meeting serving as the primary opportunity to gather informed feedback and generate ideas for renovation efforts. A review of KPI1.SE and KPI2.SE measurements highlight strong outreach and engagement across co-creation activities, confirming that all target stakeholder groups actively participated in the co-design process as planned. However, while the outreach of participants has been high throughout time, outreach of stakeholders (KPI2SE) has been progressively lower after phase 2.

Table 3: Social Engagement Indicators for Trieste demo site

KPI code and name	Stakeholder Outreach (KPI1.SE)	Stakeholders Groups (KPI2.SE)
KPI definition	This KPI measures the number of stakeholders engaged in the LH for each activity conducted (e.g., co-design sessions, capacity building sessions, community events) according to the target set	This KPI assesses the participation of all stakeholders' groups that the activity aims to engage in the event. For instance, if a workshop involving tenants, students and local association has been planned, it is important to verify that all stakeholders' groups have participated.
Unit of measurement	%	%
Kick of meeting of the project	(49 participants / 35 target) 140%	(6 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 75%
Engagement Activity 6 - Co-design session 1	(13 participants / 12 target) = 108%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%
Engagement Activity 7 - Co-design session 2	(13 participants / 12 target) = 108%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%

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Engagement Activity 8 - Co-design session 3	(13 participants / 12 target) = 108%	(2 SH categories participated / 2 target SH) = 100%
Engagement Activity 9- Co-design session 4	(13 participants / 13 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 25%
Engagement Activity 10 - Co-design session 5	(10 participants / 10 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 25%
Engagement Activity 11 - LIVING LAB BOX		
Engagement Activity 12 - Co-design session 6	(15 participants / 15 target) = 100%	(3 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 37,5%
Engagement Activity 13 - Co-design session 7	(15 participants / 10 target) = 150%	(3 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 37,5%
Engagement Activity 14 - Co-design session 8	(11 participants / 11 target) = 100%	(3 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 37,5%
Engagement Activity 15 - Living lab's activities	(40 participants / 40 target) = 100%	(2 SH categories participated / 8 target SH) = 25%

2.2. Social Acceptance Analysis and Monitoring

2.2.1. Overview of the Questionnaire and the Social Acceptance Indicators

In Task 1.2, the project aimed at assessing its impact on social acceptance and engagement regarding the proposed interventions, employing a comprehensive evaluation framework based on specific KPIs, detailed in **D1.2 – Engagement Strategy and Social Acceptance KPIs**. These KPIs were carefully crafted using both top-down and bottom-up approaches. The top-down approach drew extensively from established academic literature and theoretical frameworks, such as Technology Acceptance Models (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). These models, particularly in the context of urban regeneration, addressed factors such as Quality of Life, Attractiveness, Perceived Benefits (e.g., comfort and well-being), Aesthetics and Social Image, and Perceived Usefulness. A thorough review of these models and associated empirical research provided a robust foundation for understanding how individuals and communities adopted various solutions. Nonetheless, their focus on information systems posed limitations, necessitating the introduction of new indicators tailored to the unique attributes of the SUPERSHINE project. Complementing this, the bottom-up approach focused on aligning the KPIs with the project's technical and social objectives, reflecting the specific goals and characteristics of all lighthouse representatives.

Development process for the KPIs definition

While the analysis of the engagement KPIs was carried out in the above paragraphs **2.1.1.1**, **2.1.2.1**, and **2.1.3.1**, as they are directly connected to the engagement activities implemented up to date by each lighthouse with their respective communities, to measure the Social Acceptance KPIs a specific questionnaire was created, adapted together with the lighthouse managers to the context of each lighthouse, and whose template is exhibited in **Annex 1**.

List of Social Acceptance Indicators

- KPI1.SA Changing Attitudes
- KPI2.SA Awareness
- KPI3.SA Perceived value for money
- KPI4.SA Perceived usefulness
- KPI5.SA Quality of Life
- KPI6.SA Perceived ease of use
- KPI7.SA Social Image
- KPI8.SA Aesthetic Value
- KPI9.SA Perceived Comfort
- KPI10.SA Bill saving
- KPI11.SA Sense of belonging
- KPI12.SA Green Areas

The questionnaire was administered during 2024, with different timing for each lighthouse, to collect the baseline data, and will be administered again in mid-2025, at the end of the engagement activities, to understand how the endline data will be influenced by the inspiring principle of the SUPERSHINE social acceptance model, namely "awareness through engagement", aiming at obtaining increased awareness and acceptability through direct involvement and engagement of the communities, in particular through community-led co-design and co-decision of solutions, increasing their sense of ownership for the intended process of renovation of neighbourhoods. In the figure, an overview of the Social Acceptance KPIs, each of which has been associated with one of the three pillars of the NEB, either "Beautiful", "Sustainable", or "Together".

The SUPERSHINE Social Acceptance KPIs

2.2.2. Analysis of Social Acceptance KPIs

The following sections - 2.2.2.1 for Riga, 2.2.2.2 for FællesBo and 2.2.2.3 for Trieste - disclose the measurement of Social Acceptance indicators in the SUPERSHINE demo sites. This data was collected through the questionnaire reported in Annex 1, which was tailored to each demo site characteristics in collaboration with demo site leaders. The tailoring included possible removal or slight modifications of questions, and translation in the local language. The actual questions asked to respondents are reported above each KPI measurement, translated in English. As planned in the

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respective engagement roadmaps of demo sites, data collection was carried out before the start of renovation works and therefore it is not influenced by the latter.

The data constitutes the baseline and endline reference for understanding the context in the demo sites, collected through the same questionnaires before and after the engagement pathway for co-created renovation works. As defined in the D1.2 monitoring framework, the comparison between the two sets of data will allow to identify the impact of the SUPERSHINE interventions on the social perception of the communities in the demo sites..

2.2.2.1. Riga

Baseline data

The indicator KPI1.SA aims at assessing the attitude to change on energy patterns in the pilots; the measurements reported above constitute the baseline situation in Riga pilot, which will be compared to data collected after SUPERSHINE interventions. The overall assessment of the pilot reveals a mixed landscape. While a significant portion of respondents recognize the effectiveness of energy measures, a notable percentage remain unconvinced. In response to the first question, 64% of participants do not fully identify as adopting energy conservation behaviours. This is likely linked to a lack of awareness regarding what such behaviours entail, as 42% of these responses were "neutral."

Regarding the effectiveness of renewable energy sources, 47% of respondents either disagree or strongly disagree, suggesting a potential lack of trust in this area. This highlights the need for engagement efforts to prioritize raising awareness and enhancing residents' understanding of the diverse applications and benefits of energy measures, with particular emphasis on renewable energy. Gathering more qualitative data could provide deeper insights into these responses. Conversely, attitudes towards recycling and waste reduction are more positive, with 52% of respondents strongly agreeing and 16% agreeing on the importance of these practices. This indicates that recycling and waste reduction are the least contentious aspects of the sustainability transition.

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

(KPI1.SA)

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 1: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

Figure 2: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 3: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

The level of awareness concerning SUPERSHINE project is not unsatisfactory; it must be noted however that some activities were already carried out in the pilot at the moment of data collection, limiting the amount data collected. From this perspective, the fact that that two-thirds of respondents are either not completely aware or unaware about the project suggests that more efforts should be done to increase the level of awareness about the SUPERSHINE project in the community. Regarding the evaluation of the investment’s value to the community, the majority of respondents view it as worthwhile. Only 10% of responses indicate that the investment is perceived as somewhat or completely unworthy.

"Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?"

(KPI2.SA)

"To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community?"

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 4: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

Figure 5: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

Considering the preliminary evaluation of interventions by respondents, the later overwhelmingly agree on the useful impact of interventions on energy sustainability in the pilot. Baseline data on the

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demo site’s context reveals that 78% of respondents agree the site already has a positive social image.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

Figure 6: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”

(KPI7.SA)

Figure 7: Social image (KPI7.SA)

Aligning with KPI7.SA reported above, 77% of respondents already appreciate the aesthetics of the buildings as Figure 8 shows.

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”

(KPI8.SA)

Figure 8: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

As Figure 9 and 10 show, the satisfaction with temperatures of interiors varies greatly between seasons. While the winter temperatures are appreciated by the majority of residents, only 13% of residents report being slightly satisfied or unsatisfied overall. However, when it comes to summer temperatures, the percentage of respondents who are only slightly satisfied rises to 65%. This suggests lower appreciation of temperature comfort during summer, though it does not indicate significant discomfort.

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?”

(KPI9.SA)

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?”

(KPI9.SA)

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Figure 9: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 10: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

As Figure 11 and 12 shows, the indicator concerning reduction of energy bills signal a high degree of expectation on a reduction in energy expenditure, with 77% of respondents believing interventions are going to have a relevant impact on their bills. Observing instead the answers concerning the perception of being integrated through community building activities, respondents are less unanimous: importantly, 6% of respondents feel not at all integrated and 26% only slightly, pointing out the need to further engage residents in activities that also have community building purposes. It would also be valuable to conduct qualitative research to understand the reasons behind these responses from one-third of the respondents.

“Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?”
(KPI10.SA)

Figure 11: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

“To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions?”
(KPI11.SA)

Figure 12: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

The use of green public spaces in the pilot is quite high, with 59% of respondents reporting that they use the spaces every day or at least often.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”
(KPI12.SA)

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Figure 13: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

The use of green public spaces in the pilot is quite high, with 59% of respondents reporting that they use the spaces every day or at least often.

Endline data

This section presents the endline data collected in Riga after the implementation of both technical and social interventions under the SUPERSHINE project. The analysis focuses on residents' attitudes and perceptions regarding energy practices, awareness, satisfaction, and community integration, comparing them with the baseline data to assess changes over time. Figures 1–3 illustrate residents' responses to statements about energy-saving habits, renewable energy, and recycling. In response to energy-saving behaviours (Figure 14), 58% of respondents agree or strongly agree, while 33% remain neutral. Regarding the effectiveness of renewable energy sources (Figure 15), 25% agree or strongly agree, 42% are neutral, and 33% disagree or strongly disagree. Recycling and waste reduction practices (Figure 16) receive stronger agreement, with 67% agreeing or strongly agreeing.

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 14: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 15: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

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"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 16: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

The level of awareness (Figure 17) concerning SUPERSHINE project remains mixed. Around 42% of respondents reported to be aware of the project's implementations. Perceived value of the interventions (Figure 18) was rated positively, with 77% considering them either worthy or very worthy.

"Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?"

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 17: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

"To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community?"

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 18: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

Effectiveness in promoting sustainable energy practices (Figure 19) was rated positively by 79% of respondents. As well as Social image of the community (Figure 20) which was perceived positively by all respondents (100%).

"To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?"

(KPI4.SA)

"How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?"

(KPI7.SA)

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Figure 19: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

Figure 20: Social image (KPI7.SA)

Concerning the building’s aesthetics, 83% of respondents rate it as very appealing, while 17% rate it as appealing, showing positive unanimity (Figure 21).

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”
(KPI8.SA)

Figure 21: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

Figures 22 and 23 compare perceived comfort related to internal temperatures respectively in winter and summer. Winter temperature comfort (Figure 22) was rated positively by most respondents, with 88% expressing moderate to high satisfaction, of which, 9% are moderately satisfied, 36% are fairly satisfied, and 18% are very satisfied. Summer ratings are lower, showing 55% of respondents as slightly satisfied, 9% moderately satisfied, 18% much satisfied, and the remaining 18% very satisfied (Figure 23).

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?”

(KPI9.SA)

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?”

(KPI9.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 22: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 23: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 24 shows perceptions on how the SUPERSHINE project interventions can contribute to reduce the respondents' energy bills. Overall, respondents are positive in this regard, with the majority (92%) of respondents agreeing moderately (15%), quite a lot (23%) or very much (54%). Perceptions of community integration (Figure 25) varied, with 58% of respondents agreeing, 25% moderately, 8% quite a lot, and 25% very much.

“Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?”

(KPI10.SA)

Figure 24: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

“To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions?”

(KPI11.SA)

Figure 25: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

Use of green space is not homogeneous as 46% of respondents declare to use the spaces twice a month or sometimes, 15% often, and 38% every day.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 26: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

Impact assessment

Comparing baseline and endline data, for Riga pilot, reveals a modest but positive shift in residents’ attitudes toward energy-saving behaviours and renewable energy. While neutrality remains high, agreement with energy conservation practices increased slightly, and scepticism toward renewables decreased. Awareness of the SUPERSHINE project remains a challenge, with only a marginal improvement, suggesting the need for continued communication efforts. Notably, the perceived value of the interventions improved, with a majority now considering them worthwhile. Aesthetic appreciation and social image indicators remained stable, while satisfaction with summer temperature comfort increased slightly. However, the sense of community integration declined, indicating that future engagement should prioritise inclusive, community-building activities. Overall, the data suggests that co-design efforts had a positive, though uneven, impact on social acceptance.

2.2.2.2. Herning – Denmark

Before delving into the results concerning the intervention’s social acceptance, it is necessary to underline that due to the Danish social housing system, FællesBo is a peculiar pilot. In fact, the Danish site underwent a four-phases engagement strategy, differently from the other two pilots which underwent a five-phases engagement road. For this reason, paragraphs concerning Herning pilot baseline and endline data will be structured slightly differently than the previous and the following ones, presenting data clustered by type of KPI investigated. Moreover, although the sample cannot be considered statistically representative of the residents in the LH, respondents were selected to reflect residents’ perceptions and opinions as closely as possible.

Baseline data

As Figure 27 and 28 show, given the role of respondents as residents’ representatives and their small number, the answers concerning awareness about SUPERSHINE project are not completely satisfactory, with 38% of respondents giving neutral feedback on their awareness about the project. The level of awareness among this category of stakeholders should be quite high, so that in turn they can inform and raise the awareness of residents. Nevertheless, all respondents agree on perceiving the renovation as worthy (Figure 28).

“Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 27: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 28: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

The interventions are perceived by respondents as highly promising in promoting sustainability in the pilot, with no apparent doubts as Figures 29 and 30 show. Respondents also agree upon the positive impact on the quality of life of residents, even though it would be interesting to collect qualitative data on the reasons for the lower degree of agreement shared by one of the respondents.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

Figure 29: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the efforts as beneficial for the residents' general quality of life?”

(KPI5.SA)

Figure 30: Quality of life (KPI5.SA)

Perceptions of the user-friendliness of solutions are generally high. However, the 38% of respondents who selected “slightly” indicate the need to monitor this aspect during future engagement activities with residents as Figure 31 shows. In terms of the community’s perceived social image, one-third of respondents do not view it as clearly positive (Figure 32).

“To what extent do you perceive the deployed technologies, such as control panels and thermostats, as user-friendly and easy to operate?”

(KPI6.SA)

“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”

(KPI7.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 31: User experience: Perceived ease of use (KPI6.SA)

Figure 32: Social image (KPI7.SA)

As Figure 33 shows, unlike KPI7.SA on social image, the aesthetic of the buildings is not seen as an issue, with respondents expressing unanimous appreciation.

"What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?"
(KPI8.SA)

Figure 33: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

The evaluation of temperature comfort appears inconsistent and varies by season (Figure 34 and 35). In winter, a notable 50% of respondents report being only slightly satisfied, highlighting the need to investigate the factors contributing to this lukewarm perception of comfort. In contrast, summer temperature comfort is more widely appreciated; however, none of the respondents express a very high level of satisfaction, indicating room for improvement even during warmer months.

"How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?"

(KPI9.SA)

"How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?"

(KPI9.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 34: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 35: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

All respondents share positive expectations regarding the anticipated impact of interventions on reducing energy bills, reflecting a high level of optimism (Figure 36). However, perceptions of community integration through community-building activities are less unanimous (Figure 37). This warrants further investigation, as all respondents are tenant representatives, suggesting that existing dynamics of integration may already be at play within the pilot.

“Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?”

(KPI10.SA)

Figure 36: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

“To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions?”

(KPI11.SA)

Figure 37: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

As Figure 38 shows, the use of green spaces seems to be not extremely frequent among all residents: nevertheless, one-quarter of respondents report to go into the green spaces every day, signalling the possible existence of a sub-group of residents that have an intense use of the green areas.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 38: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

Endline data

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

The following charts and data illustrate the representatives' views on the implementation of SUPERSHINE interventions in the Herning pilot. KPI1 aims at assessing awareness of appropriate energy-efficient habits for residents of the LH. Regarding energy-saving behaviours (Figure 39), only 20% of respondents agreed, and 40% had not strong opinions. On the importance of renewable energy sources (Figure 40), all respondents agreed (40%) or strongly agreed (60%). This suggests high awareness on efficient energy habits. Recycling and waste reduction practices (Figure 41) were positively rated, with 80% agreeing and 20% remaining neutral.

“The majority of residents at FællesBo contribute to saving energy by practicing habits such as turning off the light when not in use, unplugging electronics and reducing unnecessary energy consumption.”

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 39: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

“Using alternative energy sources, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our dependence on traditional energy sources, such as fossil fuels. By utilizing renewable resources, we can reduce our carbon footprint, reduce environmental impact and promote a more sustainable energy future.”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 40: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

“Reusing items, reusing materials and minimizing waste generation not only helps conserve natural resources and protect the environment, but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes, we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations.”

(KPI12.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 41: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

In this pilot, KPI2 has been measured through five different questions to get insights on respondents' awareness on the project implementation. Awareness of SUPERSHINE interventions varied across topics remaining overall quite high (Figures 42-46). General awareness (Figure 42) was high, with 20% of respondents being fully aware, 60% quite aware. Awareness on energy management and energy saving measures (Figure 43) was unanimous with all respondents being quite aware. Awareness on solar energy initiatives (Figure 44) was lower, with 60% of respondents disagreeing. The remaining 40% rated neutral. Awareness on the recycling of building materials (Figure 45) was high, with all the respondents rating either very aware (60%) or fully aware (40%). Awareness on the increased wild nature and biodiversity at FællesBo department (Figure 46), is quite high: 20% of respondents fully agree, 60% agree and 20% remain moderate.

“Are you aware of the ongoing efforts that are being worked on as part of the EU project Supershine?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 42: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“Are you aware that FællesBo works with measures regarding energy management and energy savings?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 43: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“Are you aware that FællesBo works with initiatives regarding solar energy and solar cells?”

(KPI2.SA)

“Are you aware that FællesBo works with initiatives regarding the recycling of building material at Holtbjerg?”

(KPI2.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 44: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

Figure 45: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“Are you aware that FællesBo works with initiatives regarding increased wild nature and biodiversity in FællesBo's departments?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 46: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

Perceptions of worthiness follow a similar pattern, although agreement is less marked compared to awareness. When asked whether the overall efforts at FællesBo were worth prioritising, 80% responded positively - 60% rated them as quite worth prioritising and 20% as “fully” worth it -, while 20% expressed slight doubt (Figure 47). Support for energy management measures was unanimous, with 100% of respondents agreeing that these efforts are important and relevant (Figure 48). However, when it comes to self-financing models for energy management, opinions are more mixed: 40% rate them as moderately relevant, 40% as quite relevant, and 20% think they are not very relevant (Figure 49). Solar energy initiatives received cautious support. While 60% considered solar cell efforts quite a lot (40%) or fully relevant (20%), 40% expressed only moderate enthusiasm (Figure 50). Interestingly, support increases when solar cells are linked to self-financing: 60% rate this approach as fully relevant (Figure 51). Recycling of building materials is highly appreciated, with 100% of respondents rating it as either very much (60%) or fully (40%) relevant (Figure 52). Similarly, biodiversity and rewilding efforts are well received, with 80% rating them as quite much and 20% as moderately relevant (Figure 53).

“To what extent do you perceive the efforts as worth prioritizing at FællesBo??”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 47: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

“To what extent do you think it is important and relevant that FællesBo works with measures regarding energy management and energy savings?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 48: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

“To what extent do you think it is important and relevant that FællesBo works with self-financing solutions in relation to energy savings and energy management?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 49: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

“To what extent do you think it is important and relevant that FællesBo works with measures regarding solar cells?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 50: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

“To what extent do you think it is important and relevant that FællesBo works with self-financing solutions in relation to the establishment of solar cells?”

(KPI3.SA)

“To what extent do you think it is important and relevant that FællesBo works with efforts regarding the recycling of building materials, e.g. from own renovations?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 51: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

Figure 52: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

“To what extent do you think it is important and relevant that FællesBo works with efforts regarding biodiversity and increased wild nature in FællesBo’s departments?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 53: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

KPI4 measures the perceived usefulness of project’s implementations. The results are moderately satisfactory concerning working with control panels and thermostats (Figure 54). In fact, agreement is high, with 20% of respondents considering them satisfactory, 40% moderately satisfactory and the remaining 40% rate themselves somewhat satisfied. On the other hand, the efforts towards establishing solar cells (Figure 55) show no strong opinions overall.

“To what extent do you think it is useful to work with control panels and thermostats that can be operated actively/interactively by residents in connection with energy management measures?”

(KPI4.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the efforts to establish solar cells as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 54: Perceived usefulness (KPI4.SA)

Figure 55: Perceived usefulness (KPI4.SA)

The aesthetics of the buildings (Figure 56) were rated positively, with all respondents finding them either quite a lot (40%) or moderately appealing (60%).

“To what extent do you consider FællesBo's departments to be an attractive place to live?”

(KPI8.SA)

Figure 56: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

Evaluation of temperature comfort appears consistent, although varying by season (Figures 57 and 58). In winter, 40% of respondents remain neutral, while 60% report being slightly satisfied. In summer, levels of slight satisfaction rise to 80%.

“How satisfied do you think the residents at FællesBo are in general with the temperature comfort in their homes in winter?”

(KPI9.SA)

“How satisfied do you think the residents at FællesBo are in general with the temperature comfort in their homes in summer?”

(KPI9.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 57: Perceived comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 58: Perceived comfort (KPI9.SA)

Expectations regarding energy bill reduction (Figure 59) were moderate, with 40% expressing slight agreement, 40% moderate agreement, and 20% more positive views.

"Do you think that efforts regarding energy management and energy savings can contribute to reducing the residents' energy bill?"

(KPI10.SA)

Figure 59: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

Perceived benefits to residents' quality of life (Figure 60) are varied, with 40% rating the impact as minimal, 40% as moderate, and 20% as neutral. Nevertheless, the interventions bring a very satisfactory result as positively perceived for their role in fostering a stronger sense of community. As shown in Figure 61, 75% of respondents agree on this aspect, and 25% of them fully agree.

"To what extent do you perceive the efforts as beneficial for the residents' general quality of life?"

(KPI5.SA)

"To what extent do you think that the efforts can contribute to the residents feeling like part of the community?"

(KPI11.SA)

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Figure 60: Quality of life (KPI5.SA)

Figure 61: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

Use of green and communal spaces (Figure 62) was reported as occasional by 80% of respondents, with 20% indicating frequent use.

“How often do you think the residents use green areas in their ward?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 62: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

Impact assessment

The comparison between baseline and endline data reveals nuanced progress in the Herring pilot. Awareness of the SUPERSHINE project improved overall, though solar energy initiatives remain poorly understood. Perceived worthiness of interventions remains positive but shows more variability in the endline. While baseline data reflected optimism about energy bill reductions, endline responses suggest tempered expectations. Temperature comfort perceptions stayed consistent, with slight improvements in summer satisfaction. User-friendliness of technologies remained stable, though solar cell efforts received mixed feedback. Quality of life benefits were less unanimously perceived, yet community integration saw a notable increase. Aesthetic appreciation remained high across both phases. Green space usage became more frequent, indicating growing resident engagement. Overall, the pilot shows positive social impact with areas for targeted improvement.

2.2.2.3. Trieste – Italy

Baseline data

The responses to KPI1.SA (Figure 63) provide insights into the willingness to adopt new energy practices at the Trieste pilot site. While the vast majority of respondents report actively contributing to sustainability measures, this majority diminishes when evaluating perceptions of the positive impact of renewable energy sources and recycling practices. Notably, the highest number of "neutral" or disagreeing responses relate to renewable energy. These results suggest that approximately one-third of respondents may lack sufficient information about sustainability measures, particularly regarding renewable energy sources. Targeted engagement activities that also focus on raising awareness and providing information on renewables could help bridge this knowledge gap.

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

(KPI1.SA)

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 63: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

Figure 64: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

(KPI1.SA)

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

Figure 65: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

The KPI2.SA indicator (Figure 66), which measures residents' awareness of SUPERSHINE interventions, reflects very low levels of awareness. This underscores the urgent need to incorporate more informational components into engagement activities and potentially organize dedicated sessions to address this gap. In contrast, the indicator measuring perceptions of renovation value (Figure 67) shows more positive results, with 69% of respondents viewing the renovations as worthwhile. However, given the high number of respondents, it would be valuable to investigate the reasons behind the 16% who deemed the renovations unworthy, as their perspectives represent a significant portion of the polled population.

“Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 66: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the houses renovation as being worth the investment?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 67: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

As Figure 68 shows, most respondents generally perceive SUPERSHINE interventions as effective in promoting sustainability: however, 10% express scepticism or potential doubt. This scepticism increases to 18% when evaluating the perceived benefits of the interventions on residents' quality of life as Figure 69 shows, with these respondents rating the impact as either "Poor" or "Very Poor". These results suggest a potential lack of trust in the interventions, highlighting the need to address concerns through future engagement activities focused on building confidence and demonstrating tangible benefits to residents.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

Figure 68: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the efforts as beneficial for the residents' general quality of life?”

(KPI5.SA)

Figure 69: Quality of life (KPI5.SA)

The scepticism reflected in the KPI5.SA measurement is further validated by KPI6.SA as Figure 70 shows. This indicator, which assesses perceived ease of use, reveals that 21% of respondents do not find the interventions user-friendly. Addressing this issue will be essential during Phase 4 (Handover) of the roadmap, with a focus on capacity-building activities. Special attention should be given to ensuring that non-expert users can easily understand and engage with the interventions.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI6.SA)

Figure 70: User experience: Perceived ease of use (KPI6.SA)

The KPIs evaluating social image and aesthetic appreciation show relatively low results, likely reflecting the current abandoned and run-down state of the pilot site. KPI7.SA, which measures social image (Figure 71), indicates that only 44% of respondents provided a clearly positive assessment of the district's current social perception. Perceptions of building aesthetics are even lower (Figure 72), with 62% of respondents finding the buildings either unappealing or very unappealing. A significant improvement in the appreciation of the buildings is anticipated following the SUPERSHINE interventions.

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“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”

(KPI7.SA)

Figure 71: Social image (KPI7.SA)

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”

(KPI8.SA)

Figure 72: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

The evaluation of temperature comfort highlights clear satisfaction with winter conditions (Figure 73). In this case, 52% of respondents report being fully satisfied, while 34% express moderate satisfaction with winter temperatures. However, satisfaction levels drop notably during summer (Figure 74). Only 38% of respondents are satisfied, and 25% report moderate satisfaction. A significant portion, the 36%, are either slightly satisfied or dissatisfied, indicating a need to address summer temperature comfort through targeted improvements.

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?”

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 73: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?”

(KPI9.SA)

Figure 74: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Respondents' expectations regarding the impact of interventions on energy bills are mixed (Figure 75), with nearly one-third expressing some level of scepticism. Future engagement activities should prioritize clearly demonstrating the financial savings achieved through SUPERSHINE interventions. KPI11.SA, which measures the effectiveness of community-building activities, reveals that 66% of respondents feel little to no sense of integration from these activities. However, it is important to note that community-building efforts have yet to be fully implemented at the pilot site. These results underscore the need to place significant focus on developing and enhancing community-building initiatives as a key component of future engagement efforts.

“Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?”

(KPI10.SA)

“To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community because of the community building activities?”

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(KPI11.SA)

Figure 75: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

Figure 76: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

The use of green spaces by residents appears consistent but infrequent as Figure 77 shows. Only 20% of respondents report using these spaces daily or regularly.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 77: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

The social acceptance analysis highlights a nuanced landscape of resident perceptions and engagement with the SUPERSHINE interventions. While there is strong recognition of the value of sustainability measures and general optimism about the impact on energy bills, scepticism remains, particularly regarding renewable energy sources and temperature comfort during summer. The low levels of awareness and engagement reflected in key performance indicators emphasize the need for more targeted informational and capacity-building activities. Community-building efforts, still in their early stages, will require dedicated attention to foster greater integration and trust among residents. Additionally, the aesthetic improvements anticipated through renovations are expected to address concerns about the current state of the pilot site. Overall, the analysis underscores the importance of transparent communication, demonstrable benefits, and inclusive engagement to enhance social acceptance and ensure the long-term success of the interventions.

Endline data

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The responses to KPI1.SA (Figure 78-80) provide insights into the willingness to adopt new energy practices at the Trieste pilot site. Most respondents (73%) contribute to energy saving habits, while 27% remain neutral (Figure 78). This marks a slight improvement in clarity compared to the baseline, where attitudes toward renewables were more uncertain. The same percentage distribution applies to good energy and recycling practices (Figure 79-80).

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

(KPI1.SA)

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 78: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

Figure 79: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

(KPI1.SA)

Figure 80: Changing attitudes (KPI1.SA)

KPI2.SA, measuring awareness of SUPERSHINE interventions, shows a divided landscape: 20% of respondents are aware, 47% are somehow aware, and only 7% of respondents declare to be unaware (Figure 81). However, all respondents agree that the renovations are worthy of the investment: 29% stating the effort as very worthy, and 71% as worthy (Figure 82).

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“Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project?”

(KPI2.SA)

Figure 81: Awareness (KPI2.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the houses renovation as being worth the investment?”

(KPI3.SA)

Figure 82: Perceived value for money (KPI3.SA)

Regarding KPI4 and KPI5 (Figure 83 and 84), respondents agree on the project’s usefulness and its benefits for residents’ quality of life, though levels of agreement vary.

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI4.SA)

Figure 83: Perceived Usefulness (KPI4.SA)

“To what extent do you perceive the efforts as beneficial for the residents' general quality of life?”

(KPI5.SA)

Figure 84: Quality of life (KPI5.SA)

KPI6.SA reveals scepticism about the project's effectiveness in promoting sustainable energy practices: 21% fully agree, 36% agree moderately, and around 14% somehow agree (Figure 85).

“To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices?”

(KPI6.SA)

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Figure 85: User experience: Perceived ease of use (KPI6.SA)

The KPIs evaluating social image and aesthetic appreciation show relatively low results. KPI7.SA, which measures social image, indicates that 20% of respondents somehow feel positively towards the pilot social image (Figure 86). Perceptions on building aesthetics show that 7% of respondents expressed a slight sense of appeal (Figure 87).

“How do you perceive the social image projected by the community?”
(KPI7.SA)

Figure 86: Social image (KPI7.SA)

“What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings?”
(KPI8.SA)

Figure 87: Aesthetic value (KPI8.SA)

As for temperature comfort (Figures 88 and 89), the results are similar across seasons. Around 10% of respondents are moderately satisfied, 60% somehow satisfied, and the rest are completely dissatisfied.

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during winter?”
(KPI9.SA)

“How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during summer?”
(KPI9.SA)

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Figure 88: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

Figure 89: Perceived Comfort (KPI9.SA)

KPI10 suggest an upward shift in optimism relative to the prior KPI: 50% agree that interventions can reduce energy bills, 43% moderately, and only 7% slightly (Figure 90). This is a positive shift from earlier scepticism. KPI11 shows a more fragmented landscape, revealing that 7% of respondents feel a full sense of belonging, around 80% feels somehow integrated, and the remaining respondents do not feel integrated at all (Figure 91).

“Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills?”

(KPI10.SA)

Figure 90: Bill saving (KPI10.SA)

“To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community because of the community building activities?”

(KPI11.SA)

Figure 91: Sense of belonging (KPI11.SA)

Figure 92 shows infrequent use of green spaces: 7% of respondents reports frequent use, around 80% of respondents somewhat use green spaces and the remaining 7% never uses them.

“How often do you use your green spaces and communal spaces within your block?”

(KPI12.SA)

Figure 92: Green Areas (KPI12.SA)

Impact assessment

Comparing baseline and endline data reveals modest but meaningful shifts in perception. While awareness of the SUPERSHINE project remains low, attitudes toward energy-saving behaviours and recycling have become clearer and more positive. This marks a slight improvement in clarity compared to the baseline, where attitudes toward renewables were more uncertain. Perceived value of the interventions has strengthened, with unanimous agreement on their worth. Satisfaction with temperature comfort and ease of use of technologies remains limited, showing no significant change. Social image and aesthetics continue to be rated poorly, probably due to the initial state of the buildings at the beginning of the project. However, expectations around energy bill reduction have improved, suggesting growing optimism. Community integration and green space usage remain areas for further engagement.

3. Replicability inputs from the fellow cities

D5.3 - Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities - Part 1, due for M26 like this document, includes the preliminary variables to create a blueprint of the SUPERSHINE social acceptance model for the four fellow cities, Belgrade (Serbia), Zaragoza (Spain), Setúbal (Portugal), and Istanbul (Türkiye). The document summarises the methodology and most significant variables used by ICONS to develop the SUPERSHINE social acceptance through engagement model, with the creation of both Social Acceptance and Social Engagement KPIs.

These vertical pillars will be matched in the second part of the deliverable (**D5.4 - Developing and Fitting SUPERSHINE Blueprints to Fellow Cities - Part 2**) with the horizontal variables of social engagement and acceptance of the fellow cities, whose context framework is traced in D5.3 thanks to the analysis of data collected with the support of fellow cities managers through a short survey on the current status of both social acceptance and community engagement.

These data were integrated with the results of a co-creation workshop held during the annual consortium meeting of SUPERSHINE in November 2024, in which DEMIR, D5.3 leader, arranged a dialogue between the representatives of the three SUPERSHINE lighthouses with those of the fellow cities, in order to promote knowledge and best practice exchange. Below, some images of the boards resulting from the activity.

In-progress replicability suggestions boards for the SUPERSHINE fellow cities

From the engagement pathway in the lighthouses, SUPERSHINE have excerpted some key replicability point, valuable across different socio-economic contexts.

In any social housing project, **involving citizens in the early design process** is crucial. This approach not only ensures that the needs and desires of the community are met but also promotes a sense of ownership and engagement. Designers, such as architects, should be trained and

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equipped to facilitate co-design with residents, empowering them to co-create and validate design choices. This model of participatory design can be replicated in social housing projects across various countries, as it ensures that solutions are locally relevant and meet the specific needs of each community. Local facilitators play a key role in engaging residents, particularly in areas where language barriers or cultural differences may exist, enhancing understanding and collaboration.

Digital tools have proven to be effective in facilitating community involvement and decision-making processes, enabling citizens to actively participate in the design and planning stages. However, it is important to consider varying levels of digital literacy among different stakeholder groups, which can differ significantly depending on age, socio-economic status, or educational background. This is particularly relevant in countries with diverse populations. The use of digital platforms can be tailored to different communities, ensuring inclusivity and broad participation. By offering training or simplifying platforms, these tools can be successfully replicated across different contexts of social housing, allowing residents from diverse backgrounds to engage meaningfully in the process.

Engaging residents in the creation of their living spaces not only raises **awareness of the potential benefits** of the interventions but also reassures them that the positive externalities (such as job creation, reduced utility bills, and improved accessibility) will meet their needs. This process fosters trust and investment in the project. As this approach is implemented in various social housing contexts globally, the focus should remain on addressing the specific needs of each community while ensuring that the benefits are tangible and accessible. This replicable model strengthens community ties and builds confidence that interventions will result in long-term, positive outcomes, both economically and socially.

After the initial co-design phase, it is **essential to maintain** the trust of the community by demonstrating that the planned **renovations are feasible and financially viable**. This requires transparency about the cost and implementation of interventions, ensuring that residents can see the reality of the plans and not just theoretical promises. In any country, reassuring communities about the financial viability of projects is a key factor in keeping trust intact. Without this assurance, opposition may arise, which could undermine the success of the initiative. Therefore, it is important to show residents that the benefits promised are achievable and sustainable in the long term.

In the lighthouses, SUPERSHINE is exploring innovative financial solutions to support the implementation of planned interventions. These solutions include the SUPERSHINE One-Stop-Shop, business plans, crowdfunding strategies, and other financial instruments designed to ensure the long-term self-sustainability of the projects. By demonstrating their potential in allowing **self-sustainability of interventions**, as well as how these financial models can be applied and tailored to meet the needs of different communities, these solutions can be replicated across a variety of social housing contexts. For instance, in Denmark, the financial model allows continuous development of interventions, ensuring the community benefits from an ongoing cycle of improvements. These approaches can be adapted in different countries, enabling other social housing projects to become self-sustaining while maintaining high standards of community involvement and long-term viability.

The model of **community-led, financially sustainable, and digitally supported social housing renovation projects** is **adaptable to different cultural, economic, and social contexts**. By ensuring that residents are integral to both the design and implementation processes, and by focusing on transparent and achievable goals, this approach fosters trust and cooperation. Moreover, the financial tools and strategies used in these projects can be customised to local conditions, making them replicable in diverse global contexts, from urban centres to rural areas.

4. Key Takeaway Aspects

Through its multi-layered engagement processes, SUPERSHINE has demonstrated how social housing refurbishment can become a catalyst for community empowerment, cultural reconnection, and sustainable urban regeneration. Far from being a technical exercise, renovation emerged as a deeply social process, requiring trust, inclusivity, and transparency at every stage. The Lighthouses in Riga, Herring, and Trieste followed different trajectories, reflecting their socio-economic, cultural, and institutional contexts. Yet, together they provide an integrated understanding of how energy-efficient refurbishment can be socially anchored and replicable across Europe.

Lighthouses pathway considerations

The SUPERSHINE engagement pathways illustrate a continuum of participatory maturity, each Lighthouse embodying a different depth of involvement. **Riga** reached *vision co-creation*: a heterogeneous and historically disengaged community was mobilised to imagine its collective future, gradually building trust through hybrid tools and visible actions. **Trieste** exemplified *plan co-design*: residents were actively involved in shaping concrete plans, embedding inclusivity, gender sensitivity, and cultural heritage into proposals that extended beyond buildings to public space and urban connectivity. **Herring**, finally, achieved *co-decision*: rooted in Denmark’s tenant democracy, residents not only deliberated but formally approved investments, exercising authority over financial and technical decisions.

From imagining futures, to designing solutions, to deciding and owning outcomes, the process underscores that successful engagement cannot be measured by participation rates alone. Its true value lies in the *qualitative depth of involvement*, with each level offering lessons for replicability in diverse European contexts.

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

The **Riga Lighthouse** confronted socio-economic precarity, cultural heterogeneity, and historically low civic participation. Engagement was structured as a phased journey: from awareness to thematic workshops, culminating in co-design through the *Tandeems* digital platform and participatory budgeting for inn-yards and green spaces. Hybrid tools allowed residents to co-create façade designs, courtyard layouts, and green management plans, while also extending participation to external experts.

Financial innovation was one of Riga's most distinctive contributions. With state-backed subsidies suspended, residents and REA piloted bottom-up approaches to financing, including the creation of a homeowners' association as a vehicle for collective decision-making and financial autonomy. The participatory budgeting of courtyard spaces introduced residents to shared management of limited resources, laying the groundwork for community-led business models at the building scale. Importantly, these experiments shifted the narrative from dependency on external grants to locally generated financial strategies, marking a significant step towards replicable, citizen-driven renovation schemes in low-support policy environments. KPI monitoring revealed strong outreach, but also fragility: two-thirds of respondents reported little sense of integration (KPI11.SA), awareness of the project was low (KPI2.SA), and scepticism about energy bill savings (KPI10.SA) persisted. Riga demonstrates that in fragmented communities, symbolic participation must be consolidated by transparent communication and demonstrable outcomes to secure long-term trust.

Riga demonstrates that in fragmented communities, symbolic participation must be consolidated by **transparent communication and demonstrable outcomes**. Its experimentation with bottom-up financing provides an important lesson for other regions lacking robust public support: legal structuring of resident associations and participatory budgeting can become foundational pillars of scalable, citizen-led business models.

The **Herning Lighthouse** built on the Danish cooperative tradition, where tenant democracy formally grants residents decision-making authority over renovations. SUPERSHINE amplified this governance culture through structured feedback, tangible projects, and capacity building. Tenant board provided systematic insights and feedback loops, confirming high enthusiasm but exposing doubts about financing models potential risks. Training on the four areas of renovation empowered staff and tenants, while biodiversity projects (beekeeping, birdhouses, insect hotels) fostered ecological literacy and intergenerational cooperation. FællesBo community explored **alternative financial pathways**, including ESCO arrangements and potential crowd-financing to support PV deployment and other EE interventions. These discussions marked a step towards aligning community ownership with innovative market-based solutions. Importantly, the **cooperative governance model itself served as a financial instrument**, providing an institutionalised framework through which tenants could co-invest, deliberate, and approve funding schemes.

Monitoring confirmed strong acceptance and ownership, yet also revealed enduring financial scepticism. Herning thus shows that even in contexts with robust participatory traditions, **financial transparency and innovative funding models remain indispensable**. The replicability of this approach lies in its demonstration that co-decision must extend beyond design and technology to include shared responsibility over financial commitments.

The **Trieste Lighthouse** integrated cultural heritage and inclusivity into its refurbishment pathway. Engagement was framed not only around technical retrofits but also around equity and urban reconnection. Vision-oriented co-design involved *Inquiry by Design* workshops, with models developed by local schools, embedding future-oriented thinking in education. Gender-sensitive planning was explicitly addressed in workshops, identifying root causes of exclusion and developing corrective design measures. Urban connectivity extended interventions beyond the Boito complex, addressing roads, utilities, and mobility, and paving the way for a potential energy community.

D1.4 Engagement for social housing refurbishment – Part 2

On the financial dimension, Trieste is moving towards the concept of an **energy community** as a structural solution to collective financing and benefit-sharing. While national regulatory and technical conditions are still evolving, the participatory discourse already highlights the willingness of residents to pool resources, share renewable energy generation, and co-manage communal assets. Unlike Riga's building-scale business models or Herning's cooperative financing, Trieste's path reflects a systemic ambition: embedding financial sustainability into a neighbourhood-scale socio-technical infrastructure. This approach acknowledges the limited affordability of individual households while leveraging collective investment and solidarity to ensure both economic and social returns.

Monitoring showed mixed results: engagement KPIs confirmed inclusivity and participation, but social acceptance indicators revealed modest awareness (KPI2.SA) and limited use of communal green areas (KPI12.SA: only 20% regular use). This underlines that financial mechanisms such as energy communities will only be socially robust if accompanied by ongoing community-building, ensuring that residents see themselves not only as beneficiaries but also as co-managers of shared assets.

Trieste therefore illustrates that **financial innovation and inclusivity must advance in parallel**: collective ownership structures can create sustainable business models only when rooted in trust, cohesion, and a shared vision of equity.

Cross-cutting lessons

Participation as a progressive pathway

The three sites illustrate a spectrum of participatory depth: Riga pioneered vision co-creation in a context of socio-economic fragmentation, Trieste translated co-created visions into plan co-design rooted in inclusivity and equity, while Herning, supported by Denmark's tenant democracy, advanced to co-decision. This shows that participation is not a uniform standard but a flexible continuum, to be adapted to governance structures and community readiness. Replication elsewhere must carefully calibrate ambitions: starting with visioning in contexts of low trust, moving towards co-design where social cohesion allows, and ultimately to co-decision where legal and institutional frameworks support it.

Hybridisation and inclusivity

A hybrid approach proved indispensable. In Riga, the Tandeems platform enabled transparent online voting and design competitions, complemented by face-to-face workshops to build trust with less digitally skilled or older residents. Trieste achieved inclusivity through gender-sensitive methodologies and engagement of marginalised groups, while Herning combined institutional tenant assemblies with informal ecological activities such as beekeeping or rewilding. In all cases, inclusivity required proactive measures: translations, facilitators, targeted outreach to elderly or migrant groups, and the embedding of cultural and generational diversity in the participatory process.

Community ownership and cohesion

Engagement resonated most when connected to identity and heritage: Riga's Soviet-era micro-district reimaged through community-led urban narratives, Trieste's Boito quarter framed within cultural heritage and gender-sensitive accessibility, and Herning's cooperative ethos made tangible through the orangery and recycled-material workshops. Yet, KPI data showed that social cohesion remained fragile: 66% of Riga respondents still reported little sense of integration, and in Trieste only 20% made regular use of communal green areas. This underlines that ownership must be cultivated

not only through consultation but also through everyday practices and visible, short-term results that nurture community trust.

Financial transparency and bottom-up business models

Across all Lighthouses, **financial viability emerged as the decisive factor for long-term legitimacy**. Residents consistently expressed scepticism towards promises of energy savings, particularly in relation to photovoltaics and energy management technologies. In Riga, the suspension of national renovation subsidies pushed the community, with REA's support, to explore bottom-up financial schemes, allowing each building to design tailored business models. This shift from reliance on top-down subsidies to co-created, decentralised financing is highly innovative in the Latvian context, and signals a replicable pathway for regions with limited or unstable public support.

In Herning, the cooperative governance model created legitimacy for rent-based financing of PV systems, yet tenant concerns about costs led FællesBo to explore ESCO and crowd-financing models together with local stakeholders and SMEs. In Trieste, financing challenges were framed within broader infrastructural and social needs: here, the community discourse increasingly linked refurbishment to the creation of an energy community, opening possibilities for shared investment and distribution of benefits. These experiments show that business models cannot be imposed externally: they must be co-designed with residents, adapted to legal frameworks, and made transparent in both risks and benefits. The emerging bottom-up financial logics highlight that residents are not merely passive recipients of subsidies but potential co-investors in their neighbourhoods. Ensuring that models are understandable, equitable, and linked to visible outcomes is fundamental to strengthening social acceptance.

Comparative synthesis of community-centred business models

A transversal reading of the three Lighthouses makes it clear that financial innovation is not an accessory component of engagement but a structural dimension of legitimacy and social acceptance. Each site piloted distinct approaches, reflecting local governance traditions, regulatory frameworks, and socio-economic realities. What unites them is the recognition that business models cannot be imposed externally: they must be co-created with residents, anchored in trust, and made transparent in both risks and benefits.

In Riga, the suspension of state subsidies for retrofits forced the community to experiment with building-scale financial autonomy. The **establishment of a homeowners' association and the introduction of participatory budgeting created the institutional and cultural foundations for residents to become co-managers of communal resources**. This bottom-up structuring demonstrates how legal empowerment and budgeting transparency can substitute for absent top-down support, offering a replicable pathway for subsidy-poor contexts.

Herning, by contrast, built on Denmark's well-established culture of tenant democracy, which naturally lends itself to co-decision on financial matters. Residents' scepticism about rent-linked photovoltaic investments did not weaken participation but instead encouraged discussion of **alternative schemes such as ESCO contracts and community-driven crowd-financing**. Here, the cooperative governance system functioned as a financial instrument in itself, allowing tenants to share both the risks and the benefits of investment decisions. This approach shows how tenant organisations can evolve into platforms for financial as well as social co-creation, a lesson particularly relevant for cities aiming to institutionalise participatory governance in the housing sector.

Trieste introduced yet another perspective, one oriented towards neighbourhood-scale solutions. The **exploration of a local energy community** signalled a systemic ambition, addressing affordability constraints not at the individual but at the collective level. By pooling resources, jointly managing renewable generation, and redistributing benefits locally, the model promises to strengthen not only financial sustainability but also inclusivity and cohesion. Although the regulatory and technical conditions are still evolving in Italy, the participatory discourse already indicates a willingness among residents to assume roles as co-investors and co-managers of shared assets.

Taken together, these three approaches form a portfolio of adaptable financial models rather than a single blueprint. Riga highlights the role of legal empowerment and transparent budgeting in fragile governance contexts, while Herning demonstrates how cooperative traditions can be extended to financial decision-making through innovative mechanisms. Finally, Trieste points towards energy communities as socio-technical infrastructures capable of uniting financial sustainability with social equity.

For the Fellow Cities, the central lesson is that **financial sustainability must emerge from co-created, context-sensitive arrangements**. Only when business models are designed in alignment with local governance cultures, residents' socio-economic capacities, and principles of fairness and transparency can social housing refurbishment achieve both legitimacy and long-term replicability.

Scalability and adaptability

SUPERSHINE's approach, **digitally supported, financially transparent, socially inclusive**, is inherently adaptable. However, the lessons learned show that replication requires contextual sensitivity: Riga's bottom-up financing is most relevant in subsidy-scarce contexts; Herning's co-decision model is transferable where governance traditions support collective ownership; Trieste's focus on equity and connectivity is particularly instructive for fragmented urban areas seeking to rebuild cohesion. The fellow cities (Belgrade, Zaragoza, Setúbal, Istanbul) thus represent testing grounds where these differentiated models can be adapted, demonstrating the potential for scaling not by uniform replication but through context-specific translation.

5. Conclusions

SUPERSHINE demonstrated how social housing refurbishment can evolve into a catalyst for community empowerment and urban regeneration. In Riga, Trieste, and Herring, the project advanced along a continuum of participation (from vision co-creation, to plan co-design, to co-decision), showing that the depth of involvement matters as much as the breadth. Beyond technical upgrades, residents engaged through hybrid tools, inclusive workshops, and cultural initiatives, while experimenting with bottom-up business models such as homeowners' associations, ESCO and crowd-financing schemes, and prospective energy communities. Monitoring confirmed both progress and challenges, particularly the need for transparent communication and trust-building around financial viability. By embedding inclusivity, adaptability, and financial innovation into its processes, SUPERSHINE provides a scalable model for diverse European contexts, proving that sustainable refurbishment requires not only technical excellence but also genuine co-created ownership.

6. Annex

Social Acceptance Questionnaire Template by ICONS

Q1. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates 'strongly disagree' and 5 indicates 'strongly agree,' please, rate the following statements: [KPI1.SA]

"I contribute to conserving energy by practicing habits such as turning off lights when not in use, unplugging electronics, and reducing unnecessary energy consumption."

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

"Utilizing alternative sources of energy, such as solar or wind power, can significantly reduce our reliance on traditional energy sources, like fossil fuels. By harnessing renewable resources, we can decrease our carbon footprint, mitigate environmental impact, and promote a more sustainable energy future."

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

"By reusing items, recycling materials, and minimizing waste generation, not only helps preserve natural resources and protect the environment but also promotes safe energy practices. By reducing the need for energy-intensive manufacturing processes we can conserve energy resources, minimize pollution, and create a safer and more sustainable energy ecosystem for future generations."

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

Q2. Are you aware of the ongoing interventions of the SUPERSHINE project? [KPI2.SA]

1. I have never heard about the project interventions.
2. I have heard about the project interventions, but I do not know much about them.
3. I have some understanding of the project interventions and their objectives.
4. I am well-informed about the project interventions and the benefits they bring to the community.
5. I am highly knowledgeable about the project interventions, especially the benefits they bring to the community.

Q3. To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as being worth the investment made in your community? [KPI3.SA]

1. I believe the project interventions are not justified by the investment made.
2. I have doubts about whether the project interventions justify the investment.
3. I think the project interventions somewhat justify the investment.
4. I believe the project interventions strongly justify the investment.
5. I am highly convinced that the project interventions greatly justify the investment made.

Q4. To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as effective in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices? [KPI4.SA]

1. The project interventions do not contribute to promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices at all.
2. The project interventions have a minimal impact on promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices.
3. I am unsure about the effectiveness of the project interventions in promoting sustainable energy solutions and practices.
4. The project interventions effectively promote sustainable energy solutions and practices.
5. The project interventions significantly and successfully promote sustainable energy solutions and practices.

Q5. To what extent do you perceive the project interventions as beneficial to your overall quality of life, considering both the building experience and access to green or communal areas? [KPI5.SA]

1. The interventions do not have a positive impact on my quality of life, neither in the building nor in access to green areas.
2. The interventions provide minimal benefits to my quality of life, with limited improvement in the building experience and access to green areas.
3. I am undecided about the extent to which the interventions benefit my quality of life, as I do not notice significant changes in the building experience or access to green areas.
4. The interventions moderately improve my quality of life, with noticeable enhancements in both the building experience and access to green areas.
5. The interventions significantly enhance my quality of life, greatly improving both the building experience and access to green areas.

Q6. To what extent do you perceive the deployed technologies, such as control panels and thermostats, as user-friendly and easy to operate? [KPI6.SA]

1. The deployed technologies are extremely difficult to use and operate.
2. The deployed technologies are somewhat challenging to use and operate.
3. I am not sure about the ease of use of the deployed technologies.
4. The deployed technologies are fairly easy to use and operate.
5. The deployed technologies are extremely user-friendly and easy to operate.

Q7. How do you perceive the social image projected by the community? [KPI7.SA]

1. The community projects a very poor social image.
2. The community's social image is generally poor.
3. I am undecided about the social image projected by the community.
4. The community projects a generally good social image.
5. The community projects a very positive social image.

Q8. What is your perception on the aesthetics of the buildings? [KPI8.SA]

1. I find the aesthetics of the building very unappealing.
2. I have negative perceptions of the aesthetics of the building.
3. I am undecided about the aesthetics of the building.
4. I find the aesthetics of the building appealing.
5. I find the aesthetics of the building very appealing.

Q9. How satisfied are you with the temperature comfort in your home during both winter and summer? [KPI9.SA]

Winter:

1. I am very uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.
2. I am generally uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.
3. I have mixed feelings about the temperature comfort in my home during winter.
4. I am generally comfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.
5. I am very comfortable with the temperature in my home during winter.

Summer:

1. I am very uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.
2. I am generally uncomfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.
3. I have mixed feelings about the temperature comfort in my home during summer.
4. I am generally comfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.
5. I am very comfortable with the temperature in my home during summer.

Q10. Do you believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce your energy bills? [KPI10.SA]

1. I do not believe that the project interventions can contribute to reduce my energy bill at all.
2. I believe that the project interventions can have a minimal impact on reducing my energy bill.
3. I am unsure whether the project interventions can contribute to reduce my energy bill.
4. I believe that the project interventions can somewhat contribute to reducing my energy bill.
5. I strongly believe that the project interventions can significantly contribute to reducing my energy bill.

Q11. To what extent do you feel integrated as part of the community as a result of the project interventions? [KPI11.SA]

1. I do not feel integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
2. I feel only slightly integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
3. I am undecided about feeling integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
4. I feel somewhat integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.
5. I feel fully integrated as part of the community through the project interventions.

Q12. How frequently do you utilize the green spaces within the community? [KPI12.SA]

1. I never use them or go there.
2. I rarely use them or go there.
3. I sometimes use or go to the green spaces.
4. I use and go to the green spaces often.
5. I use and go to the green spaces very often.